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Executive Summary

This deliverable, **D1.4 | SOTERIA frameworks for safer urban environments**, presents the architectural framework of the SOTERIA project, which aims to enhance urban safety for **Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) and micro-mobility users** through integrated, data-driven, and interoperable solutions. The report outlines a comprehensive framework that supports the development, deployment, and certification of safety services in complex urban environments.

The SOTERIA integrated framework is composed of **16 components** encompassing: data management and representations, accident modelling and prediction, sensor kits, demand forecasting, safe and clean routing, behavioural tools and user information services and visualisation tools. These components collectively enable real-time data collection, risk analysis, predictive modelling, and user-centric safety interventions.

Key innovations include:

- a **modular architecture** enabling flexible integration of safety services;
- advanced **artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning techniques** for accident prediction and explainability;
- **sensor kits** and **real-time road safety analysis** tools;
- user-centric and behavioural **safety services**; and
- customisable **safety applications** for mobile devices and the web.

Furthermore, the deliverable introduces a **Safe City Certification** development methodology, which proposes a multidimensional assessment system based on multiple dimensions of urban road safety: physical, digital, social, and systemic. This system integrates both objective indicators (e.g. accident data, infrastructure quality) and subjective perceptions (e.g. feelings of safety) to evaluate and certify urban areas. The certification model is designed to be scalable, transferable, and adaptable to diverse urban contexts, offering a structured pathway for continuous safety improvement.

The proposed framework has been utilised for the technical implementations in Work Packages (WPs) 2 and 3. The framework is designed to be piloted in the SOTERIA Living Labs (LLs). It provides a strategic vision for integrating safety into transportation services, aligning with broader European goals for safe and sustainable urban environments.

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Abbreviations & Acronyms

AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
API	Application Programming Interface
CaDaS	Common Accident Data Set
CARE	Community Road Accident Database
CKAN	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
CSV	Comma-Separated Value
CVD	Connected Vehicle Data
DLAP	Deep Learning Accident Prediction
GLM	Generalised Linear Model
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LL	Living Lab
ML	Machine Learning
MND	Mobile Network Data
OD	Origin Destination
OSM	OpenStreetMap
PM	Particulate Matter
REST	Representational State Transfer
SD	Secure Digital
SDK	Software Development Kit
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMDS	Safe Mobility Data Space
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence

1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives of the deliverable

The growing complexity of urban environments, along with the increasing needs of diverse road users — especially vulnerable groups such as pedestrians, cyclists, the elderly, and micro-mobility users — demands a comprehensive and integrated approach to urban safety. Deliverable D1.4 |SOTERIA frameworks for safer urban environments of the SOTERIA project addresses this challenge by developing a structured framework to assess and enhance safety in urban areas. This deliverable builds on the conceptual and non-technical specifications presented in deliverable D1.2 | Requirements and SOTERIA architecture and provides a detailed framework for creating safer urban environments. Each component and model developed as part of the SOTERIA project is described with various technical information, including:

- component overview and design
- specification of interfaces
- deployment approach
- testing methodology
- non-functional requirements.

Additionally, the deliverable introduces a methodology called Safe City Certification for evaluating urban safety. This methodology takes a multidimensional approach, incorporating physical, digital, social, and systemic attributes into road safety assessments. The primary output is a Safe City Certification system that facilitates the comparative evaluation and continuous improvement of urban safety.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The document is structured into six main sections and one appendix, each addressing a specific aspect of the SOTERIA framework:

- **Section 2** introduces the theoretical and methodological basis for the Safe City Certification approach that evaluates urban safety across four dimensions. Furthermore, it outlines the selection of indicators, scoring logic, and application use cases for the proposed approach.
- **Section 3** presents the SOTERIA integrated framework for urban safety. This framework includes detailed designs of 16 components and models, along with their interfaces, non-functional requirements, and deployment approaches. Additionally, the section specifies the testing conducted to ensure the correct functioning of each component.
- **Section 4** summarises the key contributions of the deliverable and outlines the following steps, including testing in LLs.

2 Safe City Certification

2.1 Introduction

The issue of safety in urban spaces is a recurrent theme in the field of transportation and traffic, urban planning and social discourse. It is particularly challenging to address the complexity of road safety for vulnerable groups such as pedestrians, cyclists and users of micro-mobility devices. To illustrate this point, we may consider the German accident study of 2024, which reported a **continued increase of 26.7 % compared to the previous year in the number of accidents involving e-scooter riders** resulting in injury or fatality [1].

Despite the absence of consistent measures and initiatives to enhance urban road safety, there is a pressing need for the development of a multidimensional and transferable system for structured assessment.

The SOTERIA project has been developed to address the problem of how to systematically record, evaluate and improve the long-term safety of cities. The project is dedicated to the development of integrated safety solutions for complex urban environments. In this section, a preliminary methodological draft is formulated for an indicator-based assessment framework. This assessment is intended to consider the **technical, social, behavioural and infrastructural dimensions of urban safety**. The purpose of the assessment system is to serve as a tool for **objective and subjective evaluation of safety in urban areas** in the view of traffic and public spaces. The framework aims to facilitate the identification of safety deficits at an early stage and establish comparability between different urban districts. It is hypothesised that this approach will allow for the justification of intervention based on data and, thereby, provide the foundations for future **Safe City Certification**.

The present section is concerned with data-driven assessment methods for traffic safety and urban development. It addresses key components of the SOTERIA framework and focuses on the Safe Mobility Date Space (SMDS), the various analysis and visualisation modules (for example, the DEKRA Vision Zero Map), and approaches to Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI).

2.2 Theoretical background

The notion of safe cities in Europe is becoming increasingly significant in the context of **Vision Zero**. In addition to the processes of urbanisation, demographic ageing and the increase in multimodal mobility, policy recommendations and the necessity for resilient and inclusive infrastructure also play a major role. It is becoming evident that safety in urban areas is not only a technical problem, but rather a multidimensional challenge that combines infrastructural, social, behavioural, and digital aspects.

The SOTERIA project has been developed to address this level of complexity explicitly, employing a systematic and orchestrated approach to the development and integration of safety solutions, with a particular focus on the needs of VRUs, especially the elderly, children and disabled people. The focus of the project is declared in the SOTERIA use cases defined in Deliverable D1.2 | Requirements and SOTERIA architecture [2].

The development of a Safe City Certification should extend beyond the scope of collecting individual data or conducting selective analyses and thus, establish a **structured evaluation process that integrates diverse data sources, systematically processes them, and converts them into a robust evaluation system using defined indicators**. This approach has the potential to enhance both inter-municipal comparability and the ongoing enhancement of urban safety. However, it is imperative to exercise caution and refrain from making judgemental or disparaging remarks concerning a city that has been designated as less secure based on the score. Certification is therefore also associated with an **ethical responsibility**. However, which factors must be considered when creating a suitable framework that enables the measurement and concrete design of urban safety?

In the context of SOTERIA, the conceptual starting point for the detailed elaboration of an operational evaluation system should be represented by the developed Safe City Certification, as outlined in this section of this report and will be elaborated in deliverable D4.3 | Solutions impact assessment. The system has been designed to be embedded in the technical infrastructure of the SOTERIA project, with the aim of addressing municipal practice.

2.3 Requirements for safety assessment

A comprehensive urban safety assessment system is composed of various dimensions that influence each other. As the following discussion illustrates, several approaches have already been introduced in a concise manner. In addition, the respective weaknesses of these approaches have been identified and subsequently demonstrated.

The programme of the Clean City Campaign analysed 36 selected capital and major cities across Europe to ascertain how cities work towards making urban environments safer, healthier, and more sustainable, with a particular focus on their progress in child-friendly transport. The selection includes a cross-section of cities that possess reliable and sufficient data and data sources, thereby representing a range of locations, sizes, and approaches to urban mobility. The focus is directed towards municipalities that fall under the jurisdiction of local authorities. The following three indicators were selected for analysis as key measures: The proportion of primary schools with pedestrianised or temporarily closed school streets is indicated. The proportion of the road network that is subject to safe speed limits of 30 km/h is indicated here. The proportion of the length of physically separated cycling infrastructure from motorised traffic is measured using various metrics, including but not limited to barriers, height differences, and distance from motorised traffic [3].

The aforementioned factors result in the following issues and consequently, a restricted certification instrument:

- restricted selection of cities and indicators for evaluation;
- boundaries of the urban area or delineation between city and municipality; and
- robustness, transparency and comparability of available data for each city.

Another approach is the City Rating of the initiative “People for Bikes” that measures the quality of the bicycle road network of a chosen city. The programme recognises cities making progress towards building better bike networks or people can apply to add a city to analysis or rating of the connected system of protected bike lanes, off-street paths, slow shared streets, and safe crossings

that enables people to comfortably bike around a city. The score a city can achieve ranges from 0 to 100, while a score less than 20 means a lack in safe bikeways or more than 80 points indicates safe bike routes. Results are from data analysis software based on six factors captured: safe speeds, protected bike lanes, reallocated space, intersection treatments, network connections and trusted data. The software scores cities in four steps: data collection (mostly from open street maps), traffic stress analysis and destination access analysis by street segment assumptions of sections and intersections as well as a score aggregation [4].

This methodology is already quite extensive and comprehensive but has the issue that only bicycle paths are rated. Districts lacking a resident population are excluded from the city-wide assessment, as the values are combined into a weighted average based on population size.

Further limitations:

- optional attendance for the evaluation programme; and
- scoring weighting with average values.

Figure 1. Screenshot of DEKRA's Vision Zero Map

The **DEKRA Vision Zero Map** concept is illustrated in the screenshot above and was planned as a role model for Safe City Certification in SOTERIA with the intention of extending it within the SOTERIA project and solutions. It involves the analysis of road traffic accidents with fatal consequences and the tracking of cities with over 50 000 inhabitants that have achieved one year without fatal accidents, in accordance with the Vision Zero initiative to eliminate road deaths by 2030. The map illustrates the frequency with which a city attains the milestone of zero road fatalities over the course of a year, employing a colour-coded legend to denote this achievement. It is worth noting that a significant number of accidents occurs in smaller towns (for example, due

to heavy commuter traffic). It is important to note that even a single incident of an accident in one calendar year can have a significant impact on the safety score. Furthermore, it is important to note that road deaths represent only one aspect of safety. It is also vital to consider accidents resulting in less severe injuries, and indeed the accidents themselves, to ensure comprehensive safety management. The approach of using a map to visualise safety levels is a good idea. It is a widely used method in accident research since its invention of DEKRA Vision Zero. Following the change in the consortium from DEKRA Digital GmbH to DEKRA Automobil GmbH, it is no longer possible to further develop, edit or adapt the DEKRA Vision Zero Map product in-house. The fundamental principle of DEKRA's Vision Zero for Safe City Certification is the conceptualisation of cities that are entirely free of accident victims or accidents. This concept will be reflected in the methodological structure of the evaluation system in SOTERIA as Safe City Certification demonstrated below.

To reiterate the factors or indicators that require examination or investigation, it is advisable to revisit the example of e-scooters. In 2024, 53.7 % of all e-scooter accidents occurred in Germany's metropolitan areas. The term 'metropolitan' as employed in this statistic denotes cities with a minimum population of 100 000 inhabitants. To ascertain the traffic safety of urban areas, it is possible to consider the absolute number of accidents in relation to the total population. Furthermore, relative figures are instrumental in facilitating meaningful comparisons between different cities. It is essential to establish a clear definition of the threshold population size that delineates urban areas from rural regions. This population size is crucial in determining the classification of cities into different levels based on their demographic characteristics. As the number of inhabitants decreases, there is a corresponding decrease in the availability of data. It is also possible that the population number is not recorded or captured on an annual basis. The selection of a time-shift is also a pertinent consideration.

In essence, the issue pertains to the identification of available indicators in correlation with the given data to provide a realistic picture of the actual traffic safety situation. There are multifaceted requirements for safety assessment.

It is important to note that safety is not only measurable, but also tangible. Vulnerable groups often experience urban spaces differently than statistical indicators suggest. Social, objective and subjective safety, as well as resilience, are all important factors.

The following aspects are of relevance:

- the subjective perception of safety is influenced by various factors, including dangerous situations, darkness, abandonment, and danger;
- the level of social participation and accessibility is measured by factors such as the extent to which children, older people and people with disabilities feel safe.

The evaluation system should be able to assess both objective factors, e.g. accident frequencies or automated reports based on sensor feedback (CYC sensor kit), as well as subjective aspects (e.g. perceived uncertainties due to reports of dangerous driving situations by users of SOTERIA tools as the REBO smart camera).

In the context of SOTERIA, which encompasses technological, behavioural and infrastructure-related solutions, the evaluation of safe cities can be further expanded, defined and consolidated with the help of the continuation of SOTERIA innovations and ideas.

2.4 Methodological structure of the assessment system

As delineated in the preceding subsection, this subsection presents a modular methodological framework for assessing urban security, based on the security dimensions described above. The objective of this study is to devise an indicator-based system that incorporates both quantitatively measurable and qualitatively interpretable components. The methodological structure is delineated as follows.

The selection of suitable indicators for urban safety is an essential step in the process. The following procedure could be followed to implement a draft for intervention:

- criterion selection (indicator-based, data available, traceable);
- integration of quantitative indicators (e.g. accident statistics, sensor data);
- extension with qualitative feedback by surveys;
- scoring systems, like weighting, aggregation, threshold values; and
- certification levels for comparability between neighbourhoods or cities.

The present study for the Safe City Certification within the SOTERIA project has selected European cities by population, with a particular focus on those involved in the LLs. The selected cities include those in Germany, Greece, Spain and the United Kingdom. Following the application of filter, 250 subjects remained for whom data was available for analysis. A comprehensive search was conducted for the coordinates of these cities. Pertinent and contemporary information regarding the city in question were annotated and compiled into a list. However, it was determined that 44 factors from the following categories needed to be eliminated due to the absence of pertinent information (0 % of data):

- commuter traffic (in and out)
- share of journeys to work
- average time and length of trip to work
- dwellings lacking basic amenities
- average area of living accommodation
- number of people in accommodation for the homeless
- proportion and number of households living in houses
- proportion and number of households living in apartments
- proportion of households living in owned dwellings
- median and average disposable annual household income
- share of land
- share of population connected to drinking water system
- number of days pollutant concentrations exceeds a limit
- accumulated pollutant concentration in excess
- annual average concentration of pollutants
- proportion of residents exposed to different traffic noise over a limit at day and nighttime
- share of early leavers from education and training (total and by gender)

A further 32 factors from these categories were characterised by data completeness of less than 2 % across 250 cities:

- cultural information (number of museum visitors and theatres, ...)
- touristic information (beds, spent nights, ...)
- weather information (sunshine hours, temperature, rain, ...)
- water information
- economical information (employed persons, household, earnings, property prices, ...)
- length of bicycle network, cost of public transport and taxi rides.

A total of 25 factors, distributed across the following categories, have been identified as potentially useful. The data for these factors is available for 90 % of the 250 cities examined:

- education level
- total deaths and crude death rate
- economically active population by age and gender
- employment level
- population (also by age and gender).

The remaining cities and indicators can be summarised as in the following picture regarding the result:

Table 1. List of cities and possible indicators

Country	City	Year	Number of private cars registered	Economically active population, total	Total deaths per year	Number of deaths in road accidents	Population on the 1st of January, total
Austria	Vienna	2014	NA	913.944	16.014	21	1.766.746
Bulgaria	Sofia	2022	NA	618.416	15.723	43	1.221.172
Czech Republic	Prague	2022	NA	NA	12.810	NA	1.275.406
France	Paris	2024	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Germany	Aachen	2023	NA	142.000	2.572	3	252.136
	Augsburg	2023	NA	170.000	3.123	3	301.033
	Bamberg	2023	NA	43.000	904	2	79.935
	Berlin	2023	NA	1.984.000	38.473	33	3.755.251
	Bochum	2023	NA	194.000	4.913	4	365.742
	Bremen	2023	NA	297.000	6.909	11	569.396
	Dresden	2023	NA	298.000	6.028	6	563.311
	Flensburg	2023	NA	51.000	1.165	1	92.550
	Frankfurt (Main)	2023	NA	434.000	6.364	13	773.068
	Hamburg	2023	NA	1.022.000	19.469	28	1.892.122
	Hanover	2023	NA	287.000	5.928	20	545.045
	Heidelberg	2023	NA	84.000	1.358	4	162.273
	Kempton	2023	NA	33.000	794	0	70.056
	Kiel	2023	NA	139.000	2.758	3	247.717
	Leipzig	2023	NA	342.000	6.891	13	616.093
	Leverkusen	2023	NA	81.000	2.032	1	165.748
	Lübeck	2023	NA	114.000	3.166	4	218.095
Mainz	2023	NA	127.000	2.036	2	220.552	
Munich	2023	NA	890.000	12.685	9	1.512.491	
Stuttgart	2023	NA	355.000	5.790	7	632.865	
Greece	Athens	2013	NA	NA	27.688	105	2.622.404
	Heraklion	2015	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	Ioannina	2015	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	Kalamata	2015	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	Larisa	2015	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	Patras	2015	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
	Thessaloniki	2015	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Volos	2015	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
Hungary	Budapest	2023	712.555	NA	20.476	43	1.671.004
Italy	Milan	2023	2.100.391	NA	36.357	110	3.580.530
	Rome	2023	1.823.155	NA	28.955	154	2.755.309
Poland	Warsaw	2021	1.460.479	NA	24.016	42	1.863.056
Romania	Bucharest	2018	NA	NA	22.175	NA	2.131.034
Spain	Alicante	2023	150.994	177.011	2.889	6	350.598
	Barcelona	2023	1.264.050	1.978.689	31.896	66	3.767.382
	Bilbao	2023	319.654	384.536	8.454	5	790.197
	Madrid	2023	2.174.346	2.680.088	38.459	71	5.115.272
	Malaga	2023	257.884	287.465	4.997	12	587.068
	Marbella	2023	78.657	77.570	1.028	13	156.153
	Palma	2023	222.372	235.863	3.225	15	430.640
	Seville	2023	399.820	425.149	7.744	24	881.124
	Tarragona	2023	60.653	68.174	1.148	6	138.326
	Torrejon de Ardoz	2023	63.117	74.811	711	2	138.197
Valencia	2023	625.721	730.344	12.663	23	1.439.503	
Turkey	Istanbul	2004	1.346.655	3.119.948	36.887	NA	9.897.599
United Kingdom	Birmingham	2018	376.607	529.000	8.537	14	1.139.249
	Aberdeen	2018	90.070	129.700	2.170	2	228.180
	Basildon	2018	86.791	88.500	1.659	NA	185.171
	Brighton	2018	89.666	163.700	2.231	2	289.275
	Glasgow	2018	181.596	301.000	6.413	NA	623.715
	Hastings	2018	37.228	46.600	1.013	NA	92.834
	Liverpool	2018	136.282	242.300	4.602	6	493.182
	London	2018	2.507.333	4.861.200	50.396	112	8.866.541
	Manchester	2018	141.048	283.800	3.378	10	546.564
	Oxford	2018	46.355	90.500	914	NA	154.455
Wolverhampton	2018	102.399	118.900	2.777	5	260.967	

The United Kingdom and Spain are two countries for which data is available for all selected cities. In the context of Germany, this source cannot provide reliable data on the number of registered private cars. The inclusion of this data would be a valuable addition to the safety assessment, particularly given that the number of cars is a significant factor in the analysis. However, it should be noted that although each selected factor is available for 90 % of the cities, only 45 % of the cities are able to provide all 5 factors for the assessment.

The subsequent section will address the logic and weighting of the evaluation process. The evaluation of the collected indicators is facilitated by a point or scoring system that assigns values on a standardised scale, depending on the indicator. The weighting of the indicators can be:

- 'distribution-based' weighting to equalize differences, with a focus on physical safety;
- 'dimension-based' weighting, as indicated using the term;
- 'aggregation-based' using weighted averages per indicator, which can be combined to form an overall safety index for Safe City Certification.

Regarding the matter of assessment, it is possible to define safety levels or certification levels based on the overall score. The employment of clear visualisations, such as traffic light-based colouring and heat maps, facilitates intuitive interpretation by decision-makers, urban planners and citizens alike. It is recommended that integration into extant urban dashboards be undertaken, with the objective of achieving comparison with the DEKRA Vision Zero Map. The integration of quantitative and qualitative data constitutes a methodological approach that will be adopted for the evaluation or assessment of SOTERIA measures in the second round of demonstrations. To enhance the system's informative value, it is imperative that the assessment framework encompasses qualitative data sources. It is at these locations that the Safe City approach, as outlined in this section, can be implemented. The resulting evaluation system will be characterised by its flexibility, its foundation in data, and its capacity for expansion through participation. This system will be suitable for pilot applications in SOTERIA LLs, as well as for long-term Safe City Certification. The introduction of a standardised rating system could be supplemented in the future by a multi-level certification model. This would not only serve to identify safe urban spaces but also act as an incentive system for continuous improvement.

The objectives of certification are as follows:

- the establishment of safe spaces is predicated on the recognition of objective and subjective criteria;
- the process of evaluating and comparing the performance of different geographical areas, such as neighbourhoods, cities or countries, using a standardised metric or set of metrics;
- the necessity for local authorities to implement concrete safety measures is imperative.

It is necessary that there is transparency towards citizens and user groups (e.g. VRUs, parents, tourists).

The primary focus of this study is the subject's integration into SOTERIA. The certification system could be incorporated into the SOTERIA integrated framework as a functional component, for example via a dashboard or visualisation tool. The evaluation and recommendation for the certification level could be made automatically based on the generated data.

2.5 Application use case

The example described in the previous subsection illustrates the potential of data-driven, participatory, and expandable evaluation systems to identify specific areas for action and contribute to the systematic enhancement of urban safety. The full potential of an urban safety assessment system can only be realised if it is embedded in existing municipal processes and planning structures. Integration into municipal practice is therefore a key success factor, both in terms of continuous application and the promotion of sustainable safety cultures. The assessment system has the capacity to be utilised across a variety of levels, with the following areas of administration being notable examples of its application:

- **Urban planning:** determining the allocation of precedence for construction measures in locations where accidents have been prevalent
- **Monitoring and reporting:** assistance in the preparation of safety reports and funding applications
- **Integration into existing urban programmes.**

The issue of road safety is of paramount importance, as evidenced by the EU's Vision Zero policy and the initiatives undertaken by police forces, as exemplified by the SOTERIA development in Madrid.

The SOTERIA project provides a technical basis for implementation through the incorporation of the SMDS, the visualisation component, and the analysis modules. The automation of data provision, evaluation, and visualisation can be facilitated through the implementation of a safety dashboard for municipalities.

2.6 Summary

In the contemporary context of increasing mobility, diversity and digital transformation, the issue of safety in urban areas is of paramount importance. The necessity for the development of innovative instruments to facilitate the attainment of certificates in urban contexts is becoming increasingly apparent. The draft assessment system for urban safety presented in this section offers an innovative approach to this challenge. The integration of objective indicators from sensor technology, accident statistics, and infrastructure with subjective perspectives derived from surveys and participation formats is a distinctive feature of the approach. The tool under discussion facilitates comparative assessments of neighbourhoods or cities, thereby identifying specific areas where action is required. The system is distinguished by its modularity, a property that facilitates its expansion and integration with existing systems, including the SOTERIA framework. It assumes that, in the long term, the system under discussion has the potential to serve as the basis for a European-compatible certification process. Furthermore, it is argued that the system can motivate cities to proactively invest in safe spaces for all users, with a particular emphasis on vulnerable groups such as children, the elderly, and micro-mobility users. From an outlook perspective, it can be stated that there is potential for further development. Testing in SOTERIA LLs is being conducted to validate the system. Data-driven automation could be added to facilitate the collection of safety data, and the utilisation of AI could help to identify risks and modify scores in real time.

3 SOTERIA Integrated Framework

3.1 Introduction

The SOTERIA integrated framework consists of 16 components and models that focus on various aspects of urban safety. It includes services for analysing and visualising accident data, machine learning and data analytics models for safety and demand management applications, sensor kits designed for micro-vehicles, and user-assisting services. A summary of the purpose of each component can be found in Table 2, while subsequent sections detail the technical characteristics of each SOTERIA tool.

Table 2. List of SOTERIA components

Component name	Component purpose
Safe Mobility Data Space (SMDS)	The purpose of SMDS is to serve as a comprehensive and extendable data repository that aggregates and harmonises multidisciplinary safety databases and sensor data. It aims to facilitate research, decision-making, and data-driven solutions in the field of safe mobility by providing a unified platform for accessing and analysing a wide range of safety-related data.
Accident data processing & analysis module	This component aims to extract data from the SMDS and process it for estimating accident frequency and severity for VRUs at section and intersection levels, as well as extracting features at section and intersection levels that will be required for the accident prediction module (e.g. signalisation, number of lanes, socio-demographic characteristics, etc.).
Labelled graph module	The purpose of this component is to store a database with a labelled graph in which nodes will represent intersections and arcs will represent sections. In this database, both sections and intersections will have associated properties that refer to different information and processed data associated with them (e.g. location, area of influence, accident risk estimation, accident severity estimation, traffic data, connected vehicle events). The information and processed data will be stored and queried by other SOTERIA components (e.g. accident data processing and analysis module, accident prediction modules).
Data visualisation module	The purpose of this module is the visualisation of the processed accident data, accident risk and severity estimations and predictions, location of hotspots, safety Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), as well as other information that is considered relevant for the safety of VRUs.
Generalised linear accident prediction models	Accident prediction models allow to calculate the accident risk for each section of the road network for different road users,

	<p>surroundings and section specifications. Thereby, the models provide a base-measure to define a section-specific accident risk to derive a weighing factor for sections, which in turn is the basis for the routing algorithm.</p>
Deep Learning accident prediction module	<p>The purpose of this component is to take advantage of the high potential of multi-modal Deep Learning techniques for estimating accident frequency and severity for VRUs at section and intersection levels by using heterogeneous data sources.</p>
XAI module	<p>The purpose of this module is to use XAI techniques to analyse the predictions and models of the Deep Learning accident prediction module to, on the one hand, ensure the fairness and reliability of these models, and on the other hand, extract insights and useful patterns that may be of interest for decision-makers.</p>
Travel demand module	<p>The purpose of this module is to reconstruct at a high level of detail the mobility patterns of the entire population of a given study area. This module extracts travel demand information from big data sources (e.g. mobile network data, Connected Vehicle Data (CVD), shared mobility operation data).</p>
Safe routing engine	<p>For a given start- and endpoint as well as a specific road user type, the algorithm calculates a safe route balancing safety gains and losses due to detours.</p>
Micro-vehicle sensor kit	<p>The purpose of the sensor kit is to integrate several sensors, cameras, radars and microcontrollers on micro-vehicles, enabling the collection of heterogeneous contextual, vehicle handling, kinematics and environmental data to minimise micro-mobility hazards of VRUs.</p>
Environmental sensor kit	<p>The environmental sensor kit is mounted on various types of vehicles and collects data on air quality (via Particulate Matter (PM) sensors), temperature, and humidity. Simultaneously, it records precise location and movement using Global Positioning System (GPS) and accelerometer / gyroscope sensors.</p>
Micro-mobility hazards mapper	<p>The purpose of this component is to design and implement micro-mobility hazards mapper service which will define the locations, types and severities of all potential accidents and hazards.</p>
Protective equipment assessment module	<p>The purpose of this component is to design and implement a protective equipment assessment service which will efficiently</p>

	assess the effectiveness of protective equipment used by VRUs under different environmental and situational conditions.
Speed advisory module	The purpose of this component is to design and implement speed advisory service which will regulate the speed of micro-vehicles according to various VRU-related factors (e.g. contextual, physical and psychological).
Safety-oriented proactivity & nudge engine	The purpose of the safety-oriented proactivity and nudge engine is to enhance and promote safe travel behaviours among individuals by developing innovative methods and services that leverage behavioural change support systems. This module aims to infuse behavioural nudges into traveller information systems to encourage safe travel practices, clean and sustainable transport choices, and multimodality.
User information services	This component will develop the frontend applications (web and mobile) to be used by VRUs and drivers for accessing the VRUs and micro-mobility safety services of SOTERIA solution.

3.2 Component designs

3.2.1 Safe Mobility Data Space (SMDS)

3.2.1.1 Component overview

SMDS is a pivotal component within the SOTERIA project, responsible for collecting, integrating, and harmonising diverse data sources related to safe mobility. It aggregates structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data, including accident data, traffic information, CVD and many more.

The core functionality of the SMDS includes data integration, harmonisation, and enrichment. It employs smart data models, multi-dimensional and semantically coded data structures to support advanced accident analysis using multivariate statistical modelling and XAI. Data standardisation and enrichment capabilities are also provided to generate additional derived attributes and features from observed data, enhancing the value of the stored information (i.e. accident data standardisation according to the Community Road Accident Database (CARE), Common Accident Data Set (CADaS) models).

3.2.1.2 Design

Figure 2. SMDS component diagram

3.2.1.3 Interfaces

Table 3. Interfaces of SMDS

Interface #	Source Component	Destination Component	Interface type
Int1.1	External Providers	Safe mobility data space	File transfer
Int1.2	Safe mobility data space	SOTERIA modules	File transfer, API calls

The SMDS has interfaces with various different external providers (i.e. VIA’s shared mobility data, Unfallatlas, Madrid municipality accident datasets etc.). For this purpose, an example of one of the interfaces will be described. Same as with external providers, the SMDS interfaces with the rest of the SOTERIA modules are described in the following subsections.

Table 4. Summary of Int1.1 (External providers for SMDS)

Data description	Aggregated connected vehicle accident data for Germany, collected from the official Unfallatlas portal of the German statistical offices. Data includes geolocation, time of incident, vehicle types involved, light conditions, road surface, accident type and severity.
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Data model / sample	UIDENTSTLAE	ULAND	UREGBEZ	UKREIS	UGEMEINDE	UJAHR	UMONAT	USTUNDE
	1220204125013262022	1	0	54	84	2022	2	19
	1220529134013152022	1	0	57	44	2022	5	11
	1220508125013982022	1	0	59	73	2022	5	12
	1220517152013752022	1	0	3	0	2022	5	8
	1220426181013142022	1	0	61	46	2022	4	19

	16221017001401169170	16	0	53	0	2022	10	11
	16221207001413256870	16	0	55	0	2022	12	16
	16221116001105235370	16	0	51	0	2022	11	7
Data format	CSV file							
Security requirements	Direct download (no encryption)							
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests							

Table 5. Summary of Int1.2 (SMDS for SOTERIA modules)

Data description	Harmonised accident datasets enriched according to the CADaS data model. These datasets are used by downstream SOTERIA components, such as the labelled graph module, for risk modelling and accident prediction tasks.)
Data model / sample	<pre>{ "accident_id": "2023S000001", "datetime": 1672535700000, "accident_type": "A-11", "accident_type_label": "Collision", "weather": "A-6.01", "weather_label": "Clear", "latitude": 40.4518981138, "longitude": -3.6675283248, "vehicle_type": "U-2.05", "vehicle_type_label": "Passenger car", "injury_severity": "P-5.04", "injury_severity_label": "Not injured", "gender": "P-3.02", "gender_label": "Female", "person_type": "P-6.01", "person_type_label": "Driver", "alcohol_test": "P-9.02", "alcohol_test_label": "Negative", "drug_test": "P-11.99", "drug_test_label": "Unknown" }</pre>
Data format	JSON & CSV files

Security requirements	Access-controlled file transfer or secured Application Programming Interface (API) (Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS), token-based access)
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc or batch-based, depending on processing pipeline execution and availability of harmonised datasets

3.2.1.3.1 Interface specifications

SMDS interfaces with a variety of external and internal components through well-defined data ingestion and export mechanisms.

Int1.1: External providers for SMDS

Those interfaces are designed to support the ingestion of heterogeneous accident and traffic-related data from third-party providers, such as national or regional authorities (e.g. Unfallatlas). The SMDS ingests raw files (typically in CSV format) containing various data, which are subsequently processed through a harmonisation pipeline. The ingestion is typically performed via secured downloads or direct file uploads to designated repositories, with metadata schemas guiding the pre-processing and transformation of the data if needed.

Int1.2: SMDS interfaces with SOTERIA modules

These interfaces enable other SOTERIA components (i.e. labelled graph module, the nudge engine, and accident hotspot mappers etc.) to retrieve harmonised and semantically enriched datasets. These outputs are made available both as downloadable CSV files and through JSON-formatted API endpoints. The SMDS ensures that all data shared via those interfaces comply with data protection requirements and retain consistent formatting. Invocation may occur either on-demand or as part of scheduled workflows.

3.2.1.4 Deployment approach

SMDS is deployed on a dedicated virtual server managed by the FRONT team. Deployment follows a manual setup process using containerised services where applicable (e.g. Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network (CKAN) for dataset exposure). The internal processing components — including data ingestion, harmonisation, and transformation pipelines — are implemented in Python and operate in a modular architecture to allow independent execution of each step.

Processed and harmonised datasets are stored in structured directories on the server and exposed to other SOTERIA components either via secured file transfer (e.g. Secure File Transfer Protocol (SFTP)) or through REST API endpoints developed as lightweight FastAPI services. Access to the system is controlled through user authentication, and component integration is ensured via predefined data schemas.

3.2.1.5 Testing

Table 6. Results of the SMDS testing

Description	Result
Unit testing was adopted to verify the correct and ingestion of external accident datasets (e.g. parsing Unfallatlas Germany, Madrid datasets), ensuring that file structures are accurately interpreted.	Achieved
Sample payloads in both CSV and JSON formats were generated to test the downstream compatibility with SOTERIA modules such as the labelled graph and nudge engine.	Achieved
End-to-end harmonisation runs were performed using real-world data from Germany and Spain to assess robustness of the full pipeline.	On-going
API endpoints for data exposure were tested using simulated component requests to validate response structure, latency, and access control.	On-going

3.2.1.6 Non-functional requirements

Table 7. Non-functional requirements of SMDS

Availability	The SMDS must maintain an availability level of at least 99.5%. Downtime should be minimised, as any interruption in availability will impact the accuracy and timeliness of safety-related data for decision-making.
Capacity	The SMDS should have the capacity to store and process large volumes of safety-related data efficiently. It must accommodate data growth as the project progresses, with the ability to handle at least gigabytes of data.
Latency	The maximum acceptable latency for data retrieval and query responses from the SMDS should not exceed 3 sec, ensuring that users can access data promptly for analysis.
Monitoring	Continuous monitoring of the SMDS availability, failure conditions, error detection, and system health is essential. Monitoring requests should be sent every 5 min, and comprehensive logging of all data transactions, including data ingestion, extraction, and transformation, should be maintained.
Extensibility	The SMDS should be designed with extensibility in mind. The initial version will support various data sources, and future versions will probably integrate additional inputs according to other SOTERIA component outputs.
Protection	The SMDS follows strict data protection policies as do most IDSA compliant data spaces.
Other notes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ It is essential to continuously review and update security measures to address emerging threats and vulnerabilities. ▪ Data retention policies and data lifecycle management should be established to ensure compliance with data protection regulations. ▪ Ongoing collaboration with IDSA is crucial to maintain secure and trusted data sharing capabilities.

3.2.2 Accident data processing & analysis module

3.2.2.1 Component overview

The accident data processing and analysis module is responsible for aggregating the raw data available within the SMDS and processing it in order to extract safety-related information of a particular area. Specifically, it uses accident data, CVD events and travel demand data, which is then stored in a labelled graph, and whose description can be found in sub-section 0.

The information is added to the road sections and intersections by buffering their geometries. At intersections, their central point is obtained, and a circular buffering area is created around them. As for sections, an irregular bounding box is created from the centre of the road, of the same size as the buffered area at intersections. In both cases, the georeferenced data components within the buffering areas of sections and intersections are assigned to them.

All the data is then used to obtain accident and safety metrics, including accident risk and severity estimations at section and intersection level, location of accident hotspots for general users and VRUs, behaviour of drivers through CVD and additional tags related to road infrastructure, traffic, weather and socio-demographics.

3.2.2.2 Design

Figure 3. Accident data processing and analysis module component diagram

This component has the following sub-components (see Figure 3):

- The data extractor is the sub-component in charge of connecting to the SMDS and extracting the harmonised raw data based on the requests of the section and intersection buffering sub-components. These are in charge of defining the buffering areas depending on the characteristics of the sections and intersections, respectively, and obtaining the data related to accidents, infrastructure, traffic, connected vehicle, weather, land use and socio-demographics within these areas.

- Finally, the section / intersection data processing components are responsible of processing the data extracted by the section and intersection buffering sub-component, respectively. The data is then used to obtain the above-mentioned outputs.

3.2.2.3 Interfaces

Table 8. Interfaces of accident data processing & analysis module

Interface #	Source component	Destination component	Interface type
Int2.1	Accident data processing & analysis module	Labelled graph	Database push
Int2.2	Accident data processing & analysis module	Labelled graph	Database push
Int2.3	Accident data processing & analysis module	Labelled graph	Database push
Int2.4	Accident data processing & analysis module	Labelled graph	Database push
Int2.5	Accident data processing & analysis module	Labelled graph	Database push

Table 9. Summary of Int2.1 (Accident data processing & analysis module to labelled graph)

Data description	Identified accident hotspots for sections and intersections, as well as for different user types
Data model / sample	<pre>[{ "type": "Feature", "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.6890546, 40.41663609999999] }, "properties": { "locationType": "intersection", "locationID": 4, "info": [{ "user": "general", "severity": "severe", "rule": "maria_severe_intersection" }], "date": "2025-04-30T23:59:59", "creation_date": "2025-06-02T11:04:07.189000", "version": "1.0" } }]</pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	N/A
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

Table 10. Summary of Int2.2 (Accident data processing & analysis module to labelled graph)

Data description	Processed accident data associated with specific sections and intersections
Data model / sample	<pre>[{ "type": "Feature", "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.6167559840015056, 40.37132020827552] }, "properties": { "num_expediente": "2024S000127", "localizacion": "CALL. VILLAR DEL POZO / CALL. MUELA DE SAN JUAN", "numero": 1, "cod_distrito": 18, "distrito": "VILLA DE VALLECAS", "tipo_accidente": "Collision", "estado_meteorológico": "Lluvia intensa", "tipo_vehiculo": "Motocicleta hasta 125cc", "cod_lesividad": 3, "lesividad": "Ingreso superior a 24 horas", "fecha_hora": "2024-10-17T01:05:00", "dia": "Thursday", "n_afectados": 4, "tipo_persona": ["Driver", "Passenger"], "rango_edad": ["De 18 a 20 años", "De 45 a 49 años", "De 35 a 39 años"], "sexo": ["Hombre"], "positiva_alcohol": ["N"], "positiva_droga": [0, 1], "grupo_tipo_vehiculo": ["Motorcycle", "Car"], "gravedad_lesividad": "Severe", "personal_damage": true, "cost": 154630, "locationID": 19360, "locationType": "intersection", "users": ["Motorcycle", "Car", "Driver", "Passenger"], "creation_date": "2025-06-02T10:58:50.079000", "version": "1.0" } }]</pre>
fData format	JSON
Security requirements	N/A
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

Table 11. Summary of Int2.3 (Accident data processing & analysis module to labelled graph)

Data description	Processed harsh events extracted from CVD that are associated with specific sections and intersections.
Data model / sample	<pre>[{ "type": "Feature", "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.6844432000000005, 40.4212466] }, "properties": { "locationID": 0, "locationType": "intersection", "event_type": "cornering_right", "event_count": 609, "total": 786, "Q": 3, "D": 9, "P": 98, "mean_avg_magnitude": 333.3727422003284, "Q1_avg_magnitude": 467, "Q2_avg_magnitude": 292, "Q3_avg_magnitude": 129, "Q4_avg_magnitude": 0, "P85_avg_magnitude": 76, "P90_avg_magnitude": 47, "P95_avg_magnitude": 19, "mean_max_magnitude": 438.11494252873564, "Q1_max_magnitude": 442, "Q2_max_magnitude": 267, "Q3_max_magnitude": 94, "Q4_max_magnitude": 0, "P85_max_magnitude": 60, "P90_max_magnitude": 34, "P95_max_magnitude": 11, "start_date": "2022-01-01T00:00:02", "end_date": "2022-06-30T23:59:29", "creation_date": "2025-03-27T12:29:23.595000", "version": "1.0" } }, ...]</pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	Encrypted data transfer
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

Table 12. Summary of Int2.4 (Accident data processing & analysis module to labelled graph)

Data description	Processed travel demand data associated with specific road sections.
Data model /sample	<pre> { "type": "Feature", "geometry": { "type": "LineString", "coordinates": [[-3.6673694282937404, 40.43453122314873], [-3.6671936728821533, 40.43467166185718], [-3.6671934999999998, 40.4346718], [-3.666689787441581, 40.43411740857502], [-3.6665384999999997, 40.4339509]] }, "properties": { "total_demand": 5.559438372634427, "num_accidents": 3, "cost": 63096, "accidents_per_1000_vehicles": 539.6228537701018, "accidentCosts_per_1000_vehicles": 11349347.86049278, "decile_accidents_per_1000_vehicles": 10, "decile_accidentCosts_per_1000_vehicles": 10, "percentile_accidents_per_1000_vehicles": 98, "percentile_accidentCosts_per_1000_vehicles": 98, "demandType": "micro", "locationID": { "u": 10192, "v": 10194, "key": 0 }, "locationType": "edge", "creation_date": "2025-06-03T15:36:20.268000", "version": "1.0" } }, </pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	Encrypted data transfer
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

Table 13. Summary of Int2.5 (Accident data processing & analysis module to labelled graph)

Data description	Infrastructure data obtained from OpenStreetMaps and associated with specific sections and intersections.
Data model / sample	<pre> [{ "type": "Feature", "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.6844432000000005, 40.4212466] }, "properties": { "ID": 0, "osmid_original": 171946, "version": "1.0", "date": "2024-06-26", "accident_risk": 3, "accident_risk_pedestrians": 3, "accident_risk_cyclists": 4 } }], </pre>

	<pre> { "type": "Feature", "geometry": { "type": "LineString", "coordinates": [[-3.6844432000000005, 40.4212466], [-3.68443254729, 40.421435243729995], [-3.6844209, 40.42164149999999]] }, "properties": { "u": 0, "v": 1, "key": 0, "version": "1.0", "date": "2024-06-26", "processedEdgeData": { "osmid": 807334397, "oneway": true, "length": 43.958718814947446, "geometry": { "type": "LineString", "coordinates": [[-3.6844432000000005, 40.4212466], [-3.68443254729, 40.421435243729995], [-3.6844209, 40.42164149999999]] } }, "roadType": "tertiary", "numberOfLanes": 4, "width": 14, "surfaceType": "asphalt" }, "processedSegmentData": { "subedges": [[-3.6844432000000005, 40.4212466], [-3.68443254729, 40.421435243729995], [-3.6844209, 40.42164149999999]] } } </pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	Encrypted data transfer
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

3.2.2.3.1 Interface specifications

Below, we define the main interfaces of the accident data processing and analysis module with the other component that interacts, that is, the labelled graph.

Int2.1: Hotspot identification

These interfaces were designed to store the accident hotspots automatically identified by the accident data processing and analysis module in the MongoDB document database where the labelled graph is stored. The data format is JSON. The data does not need to be encrypted as it is not sensitive, being open data. The call to this interface is on demand.

Int2.2: Processed accident data

These interfaces were designed to store the accident data processed by this module in the MongoDB document database mentioned above. The data format is JSON. Similar to the previous interface, the data does not need to be encrypted as it is not sensitive, being open data. The call to this interface is on demand.

Int2.3: Connected vehicle data

These interfaces were designed to store the harsh events extracted from connected vehicle data and processed by this module in the MongoDB document database mentioned above. The data format is JSON. In this case, the data is encrypted as it is commercially sensitive. The call to this interface is on demand.

Int2.4: Travel demand data

These interfaces were designed to store the travel demand data produced by the respective module and processed by this one in the MongoDB document database mentioned above. The data format is JSON. Similar to the previous interface, the data is encrypted as it is commercially sensitive. The call to this interface is on demand.

Int2.5: Infrastructure data

These interfaces were designed to store the infrastructure data extracted by this module from OpenStreetMaps in the MongoDB document database mentioned above. The data format is JSON. In this case, the data is not encrypted as non-sensitive. The call to this interface is on demand.

3.2.2.4 Deployment approach

The described component is currently deployed within the UDEUSTO's facilities. All the functionalities mentioned are done through a Python instance, which connects to the SMDS to retrieve the relevant data for the module. Additionally, the module connects to OpenStreetMap³ via Overpass⁴ to obtain the infrastructure data (such as pedestrian crossings, traffic lights, bus stops or cycling lanes) of the desired city. Once obtained, the data is then processed and aggregated, and the results are uploaded to a local server within the university, ready to be used by other modules within the project.

The most notable Python libraries used are the following: GeoPandas and NumPy, which provide a useful data-structure for analysis and processing, and are a standard in the field. OSMnx provides a simple interface for geospatial queries to Overpass, which returns a raw NetworkX

³ <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>

⁴ <http://overpass-turbo.eu/>

graph of the desired area. Lastly, Shapely is used to work with the geometries and creating the buffering areas around the sections and intersections.

3.2.2.5 Testing

Table 14. Results from testing the accident data processing & analysis module

Description	Result
<p>Unit testing was adopted to ensure correct working and data ingestion into the labelled graph of the following interfaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Int2.1 ▪ Int2.2 ▪ Int2.3 ▪ Int2.4 ▪ Int2.5 	Achieved
<p>Sample payloads were created to test the responses from the API endpoints as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Using accident data from Madrid in CSV format for Int 2.1 and Int2.2 ▪ Using CVD provided by VIA in CSV format for a period of up to 9 months for Int2.3 ▪ Using travel demand data provided by NOMMON in JSON format for Int2.4 ▪ Using Infrastructure data from OpenStreetMaps in XML format for Int2.5 	Achieved

3.2.2.6 Non-functional requirements

Table 15. Non-functional requirements for the accident data processing & analysis module

Availability	<p>Level of availability required: The component must be operational at least six hours a day to make the corresponding updates.</p> <p>Impact of downtime on the operation of the platform: Module downtime will impact on the accident risk and severity estimation and hotspot location, as they will be outdated.</p> <p>Reliability: The component cannot malfunction more than three consecutive days.</p>
Capacity	The component can obtain the updated data from the SMDS and store the outputs in the labelled graph on recurrent requests (e.g. every 24 hours).
Latency	The maximum acceptable time for information processing is 24 hours.

Monitoring	Every time the output is updated and stored in the labelled graph, it must be logged.
Extensibility	The first version of the component will be developed for a specific and controlled area in each LL in which it will be tested, typically a city. In the second version, the component will allow the scalability to wider areas.

3.2.3 Labelled graph module

3.2.3.1 Component overview

The labelled graph module is a core backend component of the SOTERIA platform, responsible for storing and exposing a comprehensive graph representation of the transport network. In this graph, nodes correspond to intersections and edges represent road segments. Each element is enriched with contextual data and predictive indicators relevant to the safety of VRUs.

The module not only serves as a centralised data repository but also provides a robust REST API to enable secure and flexible access to the stored information. This API allows other components of the SOTERIA ecosystem (e.g. accident prediction, visualisation, and advisory modules) to retrieve data filtered by location, time range, user type, and geographic geometry, as well as to extract derived statistics.

The component supports a wide range of queries, including:

- retrieval of all nodes or edges in a given location or within a bounding box;
- filtering of nodes or segments by accident risk level, severity, or user type (e.g. pedestrian, cyclist);
- extraction of accident and near-miss data aggregated by time (year / month) or spatial geometry (polygon, viewport);
- access to connected vehicle events and indicators by percentile filtering (e.g. braking, acceleration, turning);
- exposure of travel demand statistics and correlations with accident rates.

3.2.3.2 Design

The labelled graph module has been implemented using MongoDB, which offers a document-oriented structure capable of flexibly storing the complex relationships and multidimensional attributes of the transport network. Each node and edge are stored as a document containing both static features (location, infrastructure type) and dynamic properties (traffic, weather, connected vehicle events, accident statistics, predictive indicators).

The system is structured around a modular schema with strong indexing capabilities:

- Nodes and edges are linked through references to represent the graph topology.
- GeoJSON formats are used for spatial filtering and queries.
- Indexes are configured on key fields, such as geolocation, accident risk, year, and type of VRU.

A major feature of the module is its API interface, implemented following the OpenAPI 3.1.0 specification. This interface includes endpoints grouped into the following thematic categories:

- **Nodes, edges, segments:** Retrieve graph elements by location, quantity, bounding box, or accident risk filters
- **Hotspots:** Get intersections or segments with high accident or event concentration, filtered by time, severity, and user type
- **Accidents:** Access raw accident data, statistics, or retrieve by spatial geometry (e.g. polygon)
- **Connected vehicles:** Extract vehicle event data and compute aggregated risk indicators by percentile filtering
- **Travel demand:** Retrieve travel demand data and correlations with accidents.

The API also supports:

- authentication via OAuth2 for controlled access;
- polygon-based filtering through POST requests with geometry payloads; and
- viewport-based filtering using northeast / southwest bounding box coordinates.

3.2.3.3 Interfaces

These interfaces are analogous to those of the previous component, since, as explained above, the function of this component is to store and make the data produced by the previous module accessible to other modules. That is why the interfaces from Int3.1 to Int3.5 are analogous to those of the previous module. In addition, it also stores and exposes the data of the Deep Learning accident prediction module and the XAI module described in sub-sections Deep Learning accident prediction module 3.2.6 and 3.2.7, respectively. Therefore, as will be seen below, these interfaces are analogous to those modules as well. Below, we describe each of them.

Table 16. Interfaces of accident data processing & analysis module

Interface #	Source component	Destination component	Interface type
Int3.1	Labelled graph	SOTERIA modules	REST API
Int3.2	Labelled graph	SOTERIA modules	REST API
Int3.3	Labelled graph	SOTERIA modules	REST API
Int3.4	Labelled graph	SOTERIA modules	REST API
Int3.5	Labelled graph	SOTERIA modules	REST API
Int3.6	Labelled graph	SOTERIA modules	REST API
Int3.7	Labelled graph	SOTERIA modules	REST API

Table 17. Summary of Int3.1 (Labelled graph to SOTERIA modules)

Data description	Identified accident hotspots for sections and intersections, as well as for different user types
Data model / sample	<pre>[{ "type": "Feature", "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.6890546, 40.41663609999999] }, "properties": { "locationType": "intersection", "locationID": 4, "info": [{ "user": "general", "severity": "severe", "rule": "maria_severe_intersection" }], "date": "2025-04-30T23:59:59", "creation_date": "2025-06-02T11:04:07.189000", "version": "1.0" } }]</pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	N/A
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

Table 18. Summary of Int3.2 (Labelled graph to SOTERIA modules)

Data description	Processed accident data associated with specific sections and intersections
Data model / sample	<pre>[{ "type": "Feature", "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.6167559840015056, 40.37132020827552] }, "properties": { "num_expediente": "2024S000127", "localizacion": "CALL. VILLAR DEL POZO / CALL. MUELA DE SAN JUAN", "numero": 1, "cod_distrito": 18, "distrito": "VILLA DE VALLECAS", "tipo_accidente": "Collision", "estado_meteorológico": "Lluvia intensa", "tipo_vehiculo": "Motocicleta hasta 125cc", "cod_lesividad": 3, "lesividad": "Ingreso superior a 24 horas", "fecha_hora": "2024-10-17T01:05:00", "dia": "Thursday", "n_afectados": 4, "tipo_persona": ["Driver", "Passenger"], "rango_edad": ["De 18 a 20 años", "De 45 a 49 años", "De 35 a 39 años"], "sexo": ["Hombre"], "positiva_alcohol": ["N"], "positiva_droga": [0, 1], "grupo_tipo_vehiculo": ["Motorcycle", "Car"], "gravedad_lesividad": "Severe", "personal_damage": true, "cost": 154630, "locationID": 19360, "locationType": "intersection", "users": ["Motorcycle", "Car", "Driver", "Passenger"], "creation_date": "2025-06-02T10:58:50.079000", "version": "1.0" } }]</pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	N/A
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

Table 19. Summary of Int3.3 (Labelled graph to SOTERIA modules)

Data description	Processed harsh events extracted from connected vehicle data that are associated with specific sections and intersections
Data model / sample	<pre>[{ "type": "Feature", "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.6844432000000005, 40.4212466] }, "properties": { "locationID": 0, "locationType": "intersection", "event_type": "cornering_right", "event_count": 609, "total": 786, "Q": 3, "D": 9, "P": 98, "mean_avg_magnitude": 333.3727422003284, "Q1_avg_magnitude": 467, "Q2_avg_magnitude": 292, "Q3_avg_magnitude": 129, "Q4_avg_magnitude": 0, "P85_avg_magnitude": 76, "P90_avg_magnitude": 47, "P95_avg_magnitude": 19, "mean_max_magnitude": 438.11494252873564, "Q1_max_magnitude": 442, "Q2_max_magnitude": 267, "Q3_max_magnitude": 94, "Q4_max_magnitude": 0, "P85_max_magnitude": 60, "P90_max_magnitude": 34, "P95_max_magnitude": 11, "start_date": "2022-01-01T00:00:02", "end_date": "2022-06-30T23:59:29", "creation_date": "2025-03-27T12:29:23.595000", "version": "1.0" } }]</pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	Encrypted data transfer
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

Table 20. Summary of Int3.4 (Labelled graph to SOTERIA modules)

Data description	Processed travel demand data associated with specific road sections
Data model / sample	<pre> { "type": "Feature", "geometry": { "type": "LineString", "coordinates": [[-3.6673694282937404, 40.43453122314873], [-3.6671936728821533, 40.43467166185718], [-3.6671934999999998, 40.4346718], [-3.666689787441581, 40.43411740857502], [-3.6665384999999997, 40.4339509]] }, "properties": { "total_demand": 5.559438372634427, "num_accidents": 3, "cost": 63096, "accidents_per_1000_vehicles": 539.6228537701018, "accidentCosts_per_1000_vehicles": 11349347.86049278, "decile_accidents_per_1000_vehicles": 10, "decile_accidentCosts_per_1000_vehicles": 10, "percentile_accidents_per_1000_vehicles": 98, "percentile_accidentCosts_per_1000_vehicles": 98, "demandType": "micro", "locationID": { "u": 10192, "v": 10194, "key": 0 }, "locationType": "edge", "creation_date": "2025-06-03T15:36:20.268000", "version": "1.0" } }, </pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	Encrypted data transfer
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

Table 21. Summary of Int3.5 (Labelled graph to SOTERIA modules)

<p>Data description</p>	<p>Infrastructure data obtained from OpenStreetMaps and associated with specific sections and intersections</p>	
<p>Data model / sample</p>	<pre data-bbox="630 365 1239 970"> [{ "type": "Feature", "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.6844432000000005, 40.4212466] }, "properties": { "ID": 0, "osmid_original": 171946, "version": "1.0", "date": "2024-06-26", "accident_risk": 3, "accident_risk_pedestrians": 3, "accident_risk_cyclists": 4 } }], </pre>	

```

{
  "type": "Feature",
  "geometry": {
    "type": "LineString",
    "coordinates": [
      [
        -3.6844432000000005,
        40.4212466
      ],
      [
        -3.68443254729,
        40.421435243729995
      ],
      [
        -3.6844209,
        40.421641499999999
      ]
    ]
  },
  "properties": {
    "u": 0,
    "v": 1,
    "key": 0,
    "version": "1.0",
    "date": "2024-06-26",
    "processedEdgeData": {
      "osmid": 807334397,
      "oneway": true,
      "length": 43.958718814947446,
      "geometry": {
        "type": "LineString",
        "coordinates": [
          [
            -3.6844432000000005,
            40.4212466
          ],
          [
            -3.68443254729,
            40.421435243729995
          ],
          [
            -3.6844209,
            40.421641499999999
          ]
        ]
      }
    },
    "roadType": "tertiary",
    "numberOfLanes": 4,
    "width": 14,
    "surfaceType": "asphalt"
  },
  "processedSegmentData": {
    "subedges": [
      [
        -3.6844432000000005,
        40.4212466
      ],
      [
        -3.68443254729,
        40.421435243729995
      ],
      [
        -3.6844209,
        40.421641499999999
      ]
    ]
  }
}

```

Data format	JSON
Security requirements	Encrypted data transfer
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

Table 22. Summary of Int3.6 (Labelled graph to SOTERIA modules)

Data description	Accident number and hotspot probability predictions associated with specific intersections
Data model / sample	<pre> "type": "FeatureCollection", "features": [{ "id": "0", "type": "Feature", "properties": { "hotspot_probability": 0.75, "intersection_id": "1", "predicted_accidents_mat_damage_only": 2.1, "predicted_accidents_severe_fatal": 1.3, "predicted_accidents_slight_injuries": 1.8 }, "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.7038, 40.4168] } }, { "id": "1", "type": "Feature", "properties": { "hotspot_probability": 0.45, "intersection_id": "2", "predicted_accidents_mat_damage_only": 1.5, "predicted_accidents_severe_fatal": 1.1, "predicted_accidents_slight_injuries": 1.2 }, "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.7048, 40.4178] } }, { "id": "2", "type": "Feature", "properties": { "hotspot_probability": 0.82, "intersection_id": "3", "predicted_accidents_mat_damage_only": 2.9, "predicted_accidents_severe_fatal": 1.2, "predicted_accidents_slight_injuries": 2.0 }, "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.7058, 40.4188] } }] </pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	Encrypted data transfer
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

Table 23. Summary of Int3.7 (Labelled graph to SOTERIA modules)

Data description	Insights from XAI methods associated with the predictions for specific intersections
Data model / sample	<pre> { "type": "FeatureCollection", "features": [{ "id": "0", "type": "Feature", "properties": { "gnnexplainer_subgraph_nodes": ["INT001", "INT005", "INT009"], "graphlime_local_weights": { "crosswalk_density": 0.42, "pedestrian_volume": 0.31, "signal_presence": 0.27 }, "intersection_id": "INT001", "most_important_features": ["crosswalk_density", "pedestrian_volume", "signal_presence"] }, "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.7038, 40.4168] } }, { "id": "1", "type": "Feature", "properties": { "gnnexplainer_subgraph_nodes": ["INT002", "INT006", "INT010"], "graphlime_local_weights": { "bike_lane_presence": 0.38, "speed_limit": 0.35, "intersection_angle": 0.27 }, "intersection_id": "INT002", "most_important_features": ["bike_lane_presence", "speed_limit", "intersection_angle"] }, "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.7048, 40.4178] } }] } </pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	N/A
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

3.2.3.3.1 Interface specifications

Here, we define the main interfaces of the labelled graph module with the other components that interact, which are mainly the data visualisation tool and the safe and clean routing module, although the interfaces are designed to facilitate interaction with other components and also external components.

Int3.1: Hotspot identification

These interfaces were designed to provide, through a REST API, data related to accident hotspots automatically identified by the accident data processing and analysis module to other SOTERIA components or external services. The data format is JSON. The interface is not secured as the data is not sensitive. The call to this interface is on demand.

Int3.2: Processed accident data

These interfaces were designed to provide, through a REST API, accident data processed by the accident data processing and analysis module to other SOTERIA components or external services. The data format is JSON. The interface is not secured as the data is not sensitive. The call to this interface is on demand.

Int3.3: Connected vehicle data

These interfaces were designed to provide, through a REST API, harsh events extracted from connected vehicle data and processed by the accident data processing and analysis module to other SOTERIA components or external services. The data format is JSON. The access to the REST API is secured as the data is commercially sensitive. The call to this interface is on demand.

Int3.4: Travel demand data

These interfaces were designed to store the travelled demand data produced by the respective module and processed by this one in the MongoDB document database mentioned above. The data format is JSON. Similar to the previous interface, the access to the REST API is secured as the data is commercially sensitive. The call to this interface is on demand.

Int3.5: Infrastructure data

These interfaces were designed to provide, through a REST API, the infrastructure data extracted by the accident data processing and analysis module to other SOTERIA components or external services. The data format is JSON. The interface is not secured as the data is not sensitive. The call to this interface is on demand.

Int3.6: Accident number and hotspot probability predictions

These interfaces were designed to provide, through a REST API, the accident number and hotspot probability predictions produced by the Deep Learning accident prediction module to other SOTERIA components or external services. The data format is JSON. The interface is not secured as the data is not sensitive. The call to this interface is on demand.

Int3.7: Insights from XAI methods

These interfaces were designed to provide, through a REST API, the insights produced by the XAI module to other SOTERIA components or external services. The data format is JSON. The interface is not secured as the data is not sensitive. The call to this interface is on demand.

3.2.3.4 Deployment approach

The module has been deployed as a containerised microservice, using Docker and orchestrated within the SOTERIA infrastructure. It comprises:

- a MongoDB instance for graph and metadata storage, and
- a Python-based API (built with FastAPI) exposing the labelled graph through RESTful endpoints.

Deployment follows best practices for scalability and maintainability:

- API endpoints are exposed via HTTPS with OAuth2 authentication for secure access;
- Data ingestion is managed via asynchronous batch jobs and real-time streams that feed into the MongoDB database;
- Geospatial indexing is precomputed during ingestion for fast spatial queries; and
- Monitoring is integrated via periodic health checks and usage logs.

The module is designed for cloud-based hosting, and backups of the MongoDB database are performed monthly, with redundancy configurations in place for disaster recovery.

3.2.3.5 Testing

Table 24. Results of labelled graph module testing

Description	Result
Unit testing was adopted to ensure correct working and data ingestion into the labelled graph of the following interfaces: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Int3.1 ▪ Int3.2 ▪ Int3.3 ▪ Int3.4 ▪ Int3.5 ▪ Int3.6 ▪ Int3.7 	Achieved for Int3.1, Int3.2, Int3.3, Int3.4 and Int3.5 Ongoing for Int3.6 and Int3.7
Sample payloads were created to test the responses from the REST API endpoints of the following interfaces: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Int3.1 ▪ Int3.2 ▪ Int3.3 ▪ Int3.4 ▪ Int3.5 ▪ Int3.6 ▪ Int3.7 	Achieved for Int3.1, Int3.2, Int3.3, Int3.4 and Int3.5 Ongoing for Int3.6 and Int3.7

3.2.3.6 Non-functional requirements

Table 25. Non-functional requirements for the labelled graph module

Availability	The module must be continuously operational, as its data are critical for real-time and scheduled analyses across SOTERIA. API endpoints must remain accessible with minimal downtime.
Capacity	Designed to scale horizontally, the module supports thousands of nodes and segments, storing high-dimensional properties for each (e.g. time series, categorical data, geolocation).
Latency	Requests to the API, including complex spatial and statistical queries, must respond within a maximum of 60 seconds. MongoDB query optimisation and cache layers ensure this Service Level Agreement (SLA) is met.
Monitoring	Service health is monitored via automated ping requests every 5 minutes. API performance metrics (response time, error rate) are logged.
Extensibility	The architecture supports the incremental integration of new data types (e.g. air quality, socio-demographics). New API endpoints can be added without affecting existing functionality thanks to its modular design and adherence to OpenAPI standards.

3.2.4 Data visualisation module

3.2.4.1 Component overview

The SOTERIA’s data visualisation module is a key frontend component that allows visualising in different formats (tabular, charts, maps, etc.) the data generated and received from other modules. The aim of the module is to be used as a tool that enables different internal and external stakeholders (e.g. cities, police departments, road authorities, the European Commission representatives) to get insights on the road safety status in the past, present, and future as available from the different LL participating in the project, as well as to demonstrate the usefulness of having such a tool for better decision making and infrastructure planning activities related to VRUs.

3.2.4.2 Design

The module is a web application (dashboard) developed with Angular and designed with the following main components:

- Login page (see Figure 4) through which users with different roles and permissions can log in into the dashboard. Currently, the user management allows for the following different users and their permissions:
 - Admin user has access to all the SOTERIA LL data
 - European Commission user has access to all the SOTERIA LL data

- Other stakeholders have access to data from one or more LLs depending on the use case. Examples are:
 - Madrid police department
 - road authority representatives.
- Guest user has a time limited log in permission with access to a selected LL data (work in progress).

Figure 4. SOTERIA dashboard login page

Figure 5 presents the homepage where the user has a quick overview of the available views of the dashboard and can manually select charts to be displayed upon login. These include the following views:

- Left side menu through which a user can select between the dashboard view and the four main views that the data visualisation tool provides.
- Views which are functionalities offered by the tool for representing LL-related information generated from different data sources. Activating a view completely updates the main section of the dashboard (all panels and filters). Each view is usually associated with a set of API endpoints.

Figure 5. Pre-homepage view where a user selects a LL

Figure 6. SOTERIA dashboard homepage with user selected widgets

Currently, the data visualisation module contains four distinguished views:

- **hotspots** (see Figure 7)
- **accidents on demand** (see Figure 8)
- **dangerous locations** (see Figure 9)
- **accidents** (see Figure 10)

with the following features:

- Panels which are the main subcomponents making up a view. Panels allow users to visualise data in different formats (maps, charts, tables, etc.).

- Layers which are togglable elements of a panel and can be hidden or displayed based on users setting. Different views have different layers.
- Filters allow users to filter displayed data. Most filters are dropdown lists and allow the user to select one or more criteria defining the data to be displayed, or the format in which the data should be displayed (for example, “hotspots view” offers the possibility to display the hotspots as individual points, clusters, or as a heatmap). In addition, a date range option is present on each view and layers.

Figure 7. Hotspots view with filters, three different view options and charts

Figure 8: Accidents on demand view with map and charts components

Figure 9: Dangerous locations view with charts and map components

Figure 10: Accidents view with map (districts shown), charts components and a comparison widget

More specifically,

Hotspots:

View of points (road segments and intersections) that the analysis tool considers hotspots. These points are calculated using a series of predefined rules based on, among other things, the number, type, severity, and clustering of accidents in a specific area. Layers are enabled to view the information by a district, aggregated, or as a heatmap. The hotspots map view allows the user to

select a hotspot point and display, in a tabular view, the list of associated accidents with their location, type, users involved, costs amongst others.

Accidents on demand

Statistics comparing the number and type of accidents in an area with the typical demand (traffic) in that same area. Points (road segments and intersections) are shown where the percentile between expected demand and number of accidents exceeds an adjustable threshold.

This view consists of two map layers and a chart area such that the default layer on the map displays points (intersections and/or road segments) where the percentile between expected demand and number of accidents exceeds an adjustable threshold. In addition, each point on this layer presents two values:

- type of accidents
- number of accidents per travel demand.

Travel demand is presented as a separate togglable layer.

Dangerous locations

Analysis of potentially dangerous points based on the aggregation of events identified in connected vehicle data. The points shown on the default view indicate instances where the percentile of different types of harsh events (brake, acceleration, etc.) exceeds an adjustable threshold. Intensities are used to represent percentiles. A second togglable layer in this view displays connected vehicle data separately.

Accidents

This is a standalone layer with a record of all accidents for a selected district or the entire area, wherever data is available. The view provides the user with the opportunity to compare between two different time periods by the following parameters:

- total number of accidents
- type of users involved
- type
- users' age range.

The frontend framework is based on Angular 19 with standalone components and Nx workspace for scalable monorepo structure and optimized builds.

Additional features include the following:

Mapping

Leaflet.js with plugins:

- leaflet.markercluster for grouping hotspots
- leaflet.heat for density visualisation
- leaflet.draw for in-map annotations and notes
- popups integrate Chart.js to display real-time demand or event evolution per segment / intersection.

Charts and analytics

The charts and analytics used in the data visualisation module are powered by Chart.js via ng2-charts. Some examples of the displayed chart formats include line, pie, bar, and stacked bar charts.

User authentication

User authentication is established through a bearer token login system.

Design and User Experience (UX)

The User Interface (UI) embraces a minimalistic design philosophy for clarity, accessibility, and focus. Specifically, clean visual hierarchy with distinct panels for filters, charts, and maps. Charts use soft, contrasting colors that adapt for light / dark modes. Icons and layout draw influence from material design principles and modern dashboard aesthetics. The interface avoids clutter — filters collapse automatically, and maps are the central focus. Careful attention is given to hover effects, spacing, border-radius and subtle shadows to enhance modern UX expectations.

The result is a sleek, unobtrusive platform supported by intuitive interactions and minimal distractions.

3.2.4.3 Deployment approach

The data visualisation module is developed using Visual Studio Code with testing in localhost. Version-control is managed via Bitbucket. The web application is built via ng build --configuration production and deployed on staging subdomains (temporary/internal). The application is self-hosted.

Figure 11. Workflow and deployment chart

3.2.4.4 Testing

Table 26. Results of data visualisation module testing

Description	Result
End2End testing was adopted to simulate user behaviour and test the following aspects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ navigation and routing ▪ authentication ▪ dashboard workflows (menus, filters, charts, maps, tables) ▪ responsiveness. 	Ongoing

Unit tests were performed to ensure the performance of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ helper functions ▪ API service. 	Ongoing
Integration tests were performed to ensure the healthy interaction of the components including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ component rendering ▪ API integration. 	Ongoing

3.2.4.5 Non-functional requirements

Table 27. Non-functional requirements for the data visualisation module

Availability	The module must be continuously operational and available for end users, as it provides critical insights into the road safety and travel demand conditions and is an important element in making infrastructural and strategic decisions.
Capacity	Designed to scale horizontally, the module supports the integration, processing, and visualisation of data of different sources and types.
Latency	Requests to the backend, including complex spatial and statistical queries, must respond within a maximum of 60 seconds.
Extensibility	The architecture supports the incremental integration of new data types (e.g. air quality, socio-demographics). New API endpoints and data volumes can be integrated without affecting existing functionality thanks to its modular design and adherence to OpenAPI standards.

3.2.5 Generalised linear accident prediction models

3.2.5.1 Component overview

Generalised Linear Models (GLMs) are widely used models in accident research to quantify multivariate effects such as infrastructure design, weather conditions, traffic patterns, topography, demographics, and land use on accident frequency. GLMs follow a typical mathematical structure consisting of regression coefficients, exponential and power functions to describe the functional link between the characteristics of a network element and the expected number of accidents on this element. Thus, GLMs as a component allow to take characteristics of a network element as input and make predictions on the expected number of accidents for a heterogenous sample of network elements as output. Deviances between the expected number of accidents from GLMs and true accidents numbers can then be used to derive the accident risk.

3.2.5.2 Design

As basis to create GLMs various georeferenced data needs to be gathered, overlaid and annotated to street network elements in order to create a raw data file consisting of indexed

network elements, number of accidents and annotated characteristics of each element (see Figure 12).

Figure 12. Process of creating raw data from georeferenced accident and environmental data

The design of GLMs in the sense of choosing significant influencing factors on accident frequency, estimating regression coefficients, choosing the type of influence (exposure or risk factor) as well as residual analysis to find systematic deviances is programmed in R. The models are created in a stepwise approach in which factors are chosen by their ability to explain differences in accident frequencies between network elements. Resulting GLMs are saved and formatted as model-files, which allow to reduce the prediction process on an import of raw data, the call of the prediction model and the export of predictions to either a csv-file containing prediction for each indexed element or to a JSON-file containing information on model details (regression coefficients, confidence intervals, significance levels, underlying distribution functions, Akaike Information Criterion (AIC)-scores, data types of input data), input data, residual analysis results, and predicted accident numbers.

3.2.5.3 Interfaces

Table 28. Interfaces of generalised linear accident prediction models

Interface #	Source component	Destination component	Interface type
Int5.1	Georeferenced raw data	GLM	CSV-file
Int5.2	GLM	Labelled graph	CSV-file
Int5.3	GLM	Micro-mobility hazards mapper	JSON-file

Table 29. Summary of Int5.1 (Georeferenced raw data for GLM)

Data description	File containing number of accidents and annotated characteristics of each indexed network element
Data model / sample	The data varies by available data in the LLs. The first column denotes the index of the street network element, the last column lists the number of accidents (of a special VRU type) on each street network element. Columns in between include annotated topographical, socio-economical or infrastructural characteristics of the environments surrounding the elements.
Data format	CSV-file
Security requirements	-
Invocation frequency	Low

Table 30. Summary of Int5.2 (GLM to labelled graph module)

Data description	File containing derived risk scores of street network elements
Data model / sample	The first column denotes the index of the street network element, and includes the following columns: "n", "risk_abs", "risk_rel", "risk_score_abs" and "risk_score_rel". Column "n" lists the number of accidents occurred on the indexed element, "risk_abs" describes the deviation between real accident number and predicted accident number, "risk_rel" returns the ratio between real and predicted accident number, and "risk_score_abs" and "risk_score_rel" include a 1 to 5-scoring of the aforementioned risk measures.
Data format	CSV-file
Security requirements	-
Invocation frequency	Low

Table 31. Summary of Int5.3 (GLM to micro-mobility hazards mapper)

Data description	File containing derived accident hotspots
Data model / sample	A structured file listing hotspots and their id, longitude and latitude of its location, number of accidents and the risk score of the accident, such as the following:

	<pre>{ "hotspot_id": 23172, "longitude": -1.2647947, "latitude": 51.777147, "accident_count": 3, "risk_score": 4 },</pre>
Data format	JSON-file
Security requirements	
Invocation frequency	Low

3.2.5.4 Testing

Table 32. Result from testing the generalised linear accident prediction module

Description	Result
Unit testing was adopted to ensure the following quality measures: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ensure uninfluenced variance of residuals (correlation of standardised residuals and prediction value, white-test) ensure low effect of singular segments on model structure / parameters (leverage, Cook-distances) ensure no systematic over-/ underestimations (test on correlation of standardised residuals and segment length, cure-plots). 	Achieved

3.2.6 Deep Learning accident prediction module

3.2.6.1 Component overview

The purpose of this component is to take advantage of the high potential of multi-modal Deep Learning techniques for estimating accident frequency for VRUs at intersection levels by using heterogeneous data sources.

This software module harnesses the power of multi-modal Deep Learning techniques to estimate the number of accidents, specifically for VRUs. It leverages the heterogeneous data produced by the multi-modal data extractor module, utilising graph-based information. The module is divided into two main components: one for training multi-modal deep neural networks and another for making predictions with the trained models. We describe both of them below.

Deep Learning training sub-module

The training component focuses on training multi-modal Deep Learning models that can estimate the number of accidents for VRUs at intersection levels. It will have the following sub-components:

- Data ingestion

This sub-component retrieves the datasets produced by the multi-modal data extractor module.

- **Model training**
This sub-component performs model training using the provided data, enabling the neural networks that are capable of handling both graph and image data such as multi-modal Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), to learn patterns and relationships within the multi-modal data.
- **Validation and evaluation**
This sub-component will assess the models using validation datasets to ensure their effectiveness.
- **Model storage**
This sub-component will save the trained multi-modal Deep Learning models for later use in the prediction component.

Prediction sub-module

The prediction sub-module will be designed and developed to apply the trained multi-modal Deep Learning models to make predictions regarding accident frequency for VRUs at intersection levels. It will have the following sub-components:

- **Data ingestion**
Similar to the training component, this sub-component ingests the multi-modal data used for prediction.
- **Model loading**
The trained models from the training component are loaded into memory.
- **Prediction generation**
The loaded models generate predictions for accident frequency and severity at section and intersection levels for VRUs. These predictions are stored in the labelled graph.

3.2.6.2 Design

The Deep Learning accident prediction module consists of predicting the number of accidents occurring at an intersection for a year. As depicted in Figure 13, it relies on a GNN considering the road network along with road infrastructure data (e.g. pedestrian crossings, parking spots, cycle lane). Travel demand data and connected vehicle data are also collected to increase the prediction’s accuracy.

Figure 13. Deep Learning accident prediction module design

The GNN used within the deep learning accident prediction module consists of a node regression, i.e. a GNN returning a prediction for each node. In this context, it corresponds to the number of accidents for each intersection. Figure 14 provides an overview of the three levels that occur within the GNN.

Figure 14. Design of three-layered GNN

At the first level, the node regression provides a prediction, i.e. a real number for the number of accidents, for each node. For this purpose, it is composed of two steps:

- neighbourhood extraction; and
- graph regression.

Given a node from which the prediction should be made, the neighbourhood extraction results in a subgraph containing all nodes within a certain range from the initial node. The graph regression then provides a prediction for the whole subgraph, thus the initial node. This predictive phase can be divided into three steps. First, the features from the labelled graph are encoded, so that each node’s and edge’s information is embedded into a fixed-size vector. During the message passing phase, each node’s information is iteratively updated according to the information of adjacent nodes and edges. Finally, the prediction step involves gathering information from each node and returning a scalar value, i.e. the prediction for the entire graph.

3.2.6.3 Interface

This interface is analogous to the one already described in Section 3.2.3, since it is the one used by this module to store the data in the MongoDB database from the labelled graph. This module provides input to other components through a REST API.

Table 33. Interface of Deep Learning accident prediction module

Interface #	Source component	Destination component	Interface type
Int6.1	Deep learning accident prediction module	Labelled graph	Database push

Table 34. Summary of Int6.1 (Deep Learning accident prediction module to labelled graph)

Data description	Accident number and hotspot probability predictions associated with specific intersections
Data model / sample	<pre> "type": "FeatureCollection", "features": [{ "id": "0", "type": "Feature", "properties": { "hotspot_probability": 0.75, "intersection_id": "1", "predicted_accidents_mat_damage_only": 2.1, "predicted_accidents_severe_fatal": 1.3, "predicted_accidents_slight_injuries": 1.8 }, "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.7038, 40.4168] } }, { "id": "1", "type": "Feature", "properties": { "hotspot_probability": 0.45, "intersection_id": "2", "predicted_accidents_mat_damage_only": 1.5, "predicted_accidents_severe_fatal": 1.1, "predicted_accidents_slight_injuries": 1.2 }, "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.7048, 40.4178] } }, { "id": "2", "type": "Feature", "properties": { "hotspot_probability": 0.82, "intersection_id": "3", "predicted_accidents_mat_damage_only": 2.9, "predicted_accidents_severe_fatal": 1.2, "predicted_accidents_slight_injuries": 2.0 }, "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.7058, 40.4188] } }] </pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	Encrypted data transfer
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

3.2.6.3.1 Interface specifications

Int6.1: Deep Learning accident prediction module with labelled graph

These interfaces were designed to store the accident number and hotspot probability predictions produced by this module in the MongoDB document database mentioned above. The data format is JSON. In this case, the data is not encrypted as non-sensitive. The call to this interface is on demand.

3.2.6.4 Deployment approach

The implementation of the Deep Learning accident prediction module relies on JAX⁵, a Python library for accelerator-oriented array computation and program transformation, designed for high-performance numerical computing and large-scale machine learning. Figure 15 details the organisation of components for this module.

Figure 15. Deep Learning accident prediction module deployment approach

The labelled graph is stored in a MongoDB. The first step is thus to extract the information from the database and transform it into a data structure compatible with JAX. For convenience, we used Jraph⁶, which has been implemented with JAX. In the same way, we trained our Deep Learning model with Flax⁷ and Optax⁸, which are the “official” JAX-compatible libraries for neural network training and optimisation, respectively. After the Deep Learning model is trained, the generated neural network is saved and reused (using the Flax library) for predicting the number of accidents. The prediction at nodes must finally be stored in the database of the labelled graph. Finally, this module has been deployed in a local server at the UDEUSTO.

⁵ <https://github.com/jax-ml/jax>

⁶ <https://github.com/google-deepmind/jraph>

⁷ <https://github.com/google/flax>

⁸ <https://github.com/google-deepmind/optax>

3.2.6.5 Testing

Table 35. Results from testing the Deep Learning accident prediction module

Description	Result
Unit testing was adopted to ensure correct working and data ingestion into the labelled graph of the Int7.1 interface	Ongoing
Sample payloads were created to test the responses from the Int7.1 API endpoint.	Ongoing

3.2.6.6 Non-functional requirements

Table 36. Non-functional requirements for the Deep Learning accident prediction module

Availability	<p>Level of availability required: This component must be operational at least six hours a day to make the corresponding prediction updates.</p> <p>Impact of downtime on platform operation: Accident risk and severity predictions will become outdated.</p> <p>Reliability: The component must not malfunction for more than three consecutive days.</p>
Capacity	The component can update the output data and store it in the labelled graph based on recurrent requests (e.g. every week).
Latency	The maximum acceptable time for information processing is 24 hours.
Monitoring	Every time the output is updated and stored in the labelled graph, it must be logged.
Extensibility	The first version of this component will be prepared only for working with data from intersections. The following version will be extended to work with both intersections and sections.
Protection	N/A

3.2.7 Explainable AI (XAI) module

3.2.7.1 Component overview

The purpose of this module is to use XAI techniques to analyse the predictions and models of the Deep Learning accident prediction module to, on the one hand, ensure the fairness and reliability of these models, and on the other hand, extract insights and useful patterns that may be of interest for decision-makers.

The XAI module is designed to provide transparency, fairness, and reliability in the context of Deep Learning-based accident prediction models. Its primary objective is to examine the predictions

and models generated by the Deep Learning accident prediction module. Additionally, it extracts insights and useful patterns from these models, enhancing their interpretability for decision-makers. By ensuring the fairness and reliability of the models and delivering actionable insights, this module enhances the trustworthiness of the accident prediction capabilities of SOTERIA solutions.

The XAI tools implemented in this module can be categorised into two main blocks:

Model fairness assessment

The module employs fairness assessment techniques to evaluate the model's predictions, ensuring that the predictions do not exhibit biases or discrimination against specific demographic groups or areas. Possible fairness assessment techniques include:

- **Bias detection:** Identifying and quantifying any bias in the model's predictions
- **Fairness-aware training:** Revising the training data or the model's parameters to reduce bias
- **Demographic parity analysis:** Evaluating the model's performance across different demographic groups.

Model explainability techniques

- **GNNExplainer:** An optimisation task that maximises the mutual information between a GNN's prediction and distribution of possible subgraph structures. It provides an explanation for a single prediction made at an intersection.
- **Local Interpretable Model Explanations for GNNs (GraphLIME):** A model-agnostic, local, and nonlinear explanation method for GNN in node classification tasks. It provides an explanation for a single prediction made at an intersection.
- **Feature importance ranking:** Determining which features have the most significant impact on model predictions.

3.2.7.2 Design

An overview of the functioning of the XAI module is depicted in Figure 166. Given a prediction made by the Deep Learning accident prediction module, the XAI module explains it by emphasising features having a strong impact on the prediction. As a first step, applying GNNExplainerⁱ filters edges and edge's feature having a correlation with the node regression. Thus, removing "non-necessary" edges and edges' features will not modify the value of the prediction. This filtering is binary. It means that edges and features are considered either "relevant" or "non-relevant". As a second step, GraphLIMEⁱⁱ gives a relationship between the filtered features of the filtered edges which is equivalent to the initial node regression. Thus, given a prediction at an intersection, the XAI module provides the knowledge of which feature (e.g. the presence of a specific pedestrian crossing) has a positive or negative impact.

Figure 16: XAI design diagram

3.2.7.3 Interface

Table 37. Interfaces of Explainable AI (XAI) module

Interface #	Source Component	Destination component	Interface type
Int7.1	Explainable AI module	Labelled graph	Database push

Table 38. Summary of Int7.1 (XAI module to labelled graph)

Data description	Insights from XAI methods associated with the predictions for specific intersections
Data model / sample	<pre> { "type": "FeatureCollection", "features": [{ "id": "0", "type": "Feature", "properties": { "gnnexplainer_subgraph_nodes": ["INT001", "INT005", "INT009"], "graphlime_local_weights": { "crosswalk_density": 0.42, "pedestrian_volume": 0.31, "signal_presence": 0.27 }, "intersection_id": "INT001", "most_important_features": ["crosswalk_density", "pedestrian_volume", "signal_presence"] }, "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.7038, 40.4168] } }, { "id": "1", "type": "Feature", "properties": { "gnnexplainer_subgraph_nodes": ["INT002", "INT006", "INT010"], "graphlime_local_weights": { "bike_lane_presence": 0.38, "speed_limit": 0.35, "intersection_angle": 0.27 }, "intersection_id": "INT002", "most_important_features": ["bike_lane_presence", "speed_limit", "intersection_angle"] }, "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.7048, 40.4178] } }] } </pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

3.2.7.3.1 Interface specifications

Int7.1: XAI module with labelled graph

These interfaces were designed to store the insights from XAI methods in the MongoDB document database mentioned above. The data format is JSON. In this case, the data is not encrypted as non-sensitive. The call to this interface is on demand.

3.2.7.4 Deployment approach

Given a prediction made by the Deep Learning accident prediction module, XAI techniques, i.e. GNNExplainer and GraphLIME, are applied using the labelled graph's features (see Figure 17). The explanation provided is subject to a human expert before being integrated to the database.

Figure 17: XAI module deployment approach

3.2.7.5 Testing

Table 39. Results of testing the XAI module

Description	Result
Unit testing was adopted to ensure correct working and data ingestion into the labelled graph of the Int9.1 interface	Ongoing
Sample payloads were created to test the responses from the Int9.1 API endpoint.	Ongoing

3.2.7.6 Non-functional requirements

Table 40. Non-functional requirements for the XAI module

Availability	<p>Level of availability required This component must be operational every time the multi-modal Deep Learning models are trained or re-trained.</p> <p>Impact of downtime on the operation of the platform Fairness, reliability and insights analysis will be less accurate.</p> <p>Reliability The component cannot malfunction in more than two consecutive requests.</p>
Capacity	The component can update the output data based on recurrent requests related to the re-trained process of the models of the Deep Learning accident prediction module (e.g. once a month).
Latency	The maximum acceptable time for information processing is three days.
Monitoring	Every time the output is updated and stored in the labelled graph it must be logged.
Extensibility	The first version of this component will be only prepared for models focused on intersections. The following version will be extended to work with both sections and intersections.

3.2.8 Travel demand module

3.2.8.1 Component overview

The travel demand module reconstructs at a high level details of the mobility patterns (travel demand) for the entire population of a given study area.

This module will be used to:

- extract travel demand information from Big Data sources (e.g. mobile network data, connected vehicle data, shared mobility operation data). This information can be used to analyse unexplored behavioural characteristics and mobility needs of VRUs from various demographic segments and understand characteristics of new types of micro-vehicles;
- analyse how travel demand correlates with accident risk and severity; and
- infer (demand related) explanatory variables for accident risk and severity prediction modules.

3.2.8.2 Design

The travel demand module utilises anonymised Mobile Network Data (MND) as its primary source, capturing interactions between mobile devices and network antennas. The algorithms are applied to reconstruct all trips performed by the members of the sample. The reconstruction of the trips includes: origin, destination and start and end time of the trip.

Additional data enriches this information by two sequential steps:

1. Machine learning techniques are used to overcome the lack of some traveller and journey information. A machine learning model is trained with survey data (e.g. household

mobility survey) and then applied to the trips observed in the MND for inferring the travel mode.

2. A combination of data sources (e.g. connected vehicle data, shared mobility data, traffic counts, etc.) are used to infer the travel route to the trips observed in MND and segmented by mode.

The information obtained is aggregated with the required spatial and temporal resolution and the desired segmentations to generate:

- origin-destination (OD) matrices segmented by type of road user (VRUs, private vehicle, public transport), age, gender and other relevant characteristics.
- Other mobility indicators such as traffic intensity per road section and segmented by VRUs (pedestrians, cyclists, etc.).

Figure 18. Travel demand design diagram

3.2.8.3 Interfaces

Table 41: Interfaces of travel demand module

Interface #	Source component	Destination component	Interface type
Int8.1	Safe mobility data space	Travel demand module	Parquet-file
Int8.2	Travel demand module	Safe mobility data space	CSV-file
Int8.3	Travel demand module	Labelled graph module	CSV-file

Table 42: Summary of Int8.1 (Safe mobility data space to travel demand module)

Data description	Files containing the connected vehicle data and the micromobility demand information
Data model / sample	<p>A table with the following columns:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ session_id ▪ timestamp ▪ latitude ▪ longitude ▪ speed ▪ heading ▪ vehicle_type ▪ road_type ▪ road_speed_limit ▪ hour ▪ date
Data format	Parquet
Security requirements	Encrypted data transfer and all trip data is anonymised
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc

Table 43: Summary of Int8.2 (Travel demand module to SMDS)

Data description	Travel demand outputs, including OD matrices and traffic flows per section
Data model / sample	<p>A table with the following columns:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ date ▪ hour ▪ way_id_and_nodes ▪ way_id

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ from_node ▪ to_nod ▪ origin ▪ destination ▪ gender ▪ age ▪ income ▪ purpose ▪ distance ▪ micromobility_count ▪ passenger_car_count ▪ motorbike_count
Data format	CSV-file
Security requirements	
Invocation frequency	Monthly

Table 44: Summary of Int8.3 (Travel demand module to the labelled graph module)

Data description	Travel demand outputs, including traffic flows per section
Data model / sample	<p>A table with the following columns:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ date ▪ hour ▪ way_id_and_nodes ▪ way_id ▪ from_node ▪ to_nod ▪ origin ▪ destination ▪ gender ▪ age ▪ income ▪ purpose ▪ distance ▪ micromobility_count ▪ passenger_car_count ▪ motorbike_count
Data format	CSV-file
Security requirements	-

Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc
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3.2.8.4 Deployment approach

The travel demand module is deployed and executed locally using Docker to ensure a consistent runtime environment. The component is launched and managed through a Jupyter notebook interface, which allows step-by-step control and flexibility during model execution and testing.

All required dependencies are encapsulated within the Docker image, including necessary Python libraries and data processing tools. Input and output file paths, as well as model parameters, are defined via configuration cells within the notebook.

This setup facilitates reproducibility and ease of use during development and testing phases. While not integrated into a production pipeline at this stage, the component architecture allows for future automation and scaling if needed.

3.2.8.5 Testing

Table 45. Results of testing the travel demand module

Description	Result
Unit testing was adopted to ensure the following interfaces: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Int9.1 ▪ Int9.2 ▪ Int9.3 	Achieved

3.2.8.6 Non-functional requirements

Table 46. Non-functional requirements for the travel demand module

Availability	The travel demand module is available on-demand and runs locally upon user initiation. It does not require high availability as it is not part of a real-time system.
Capacity	The component can predict each travel mode with an accuracy higher than 1.5 times its percentage in the sample.
Latency	No real-time application so there are no latency requirements.
Monitoring	Monitoring is manual and performed through the Jupyter notebook interface.
Extensibility	The codebase is modular and can be extended to incorporate new modes, data sources, or demand modelling approaches. Configuration files and

	code cells are structured to allow easy parameter changes and adaptation to new input/output schemes.
Protection	The raw MND must be processed in the infrastructure of the MNO and no individual data will be shared. Aggregated data obtained by NOMMON for the Madrid city will be shared with the consortium under a licenced agreement.
Other notes	The component is currently used in a research and prototyping context, executed manually through Jupyter notebooks. In the future, it can be automated and integrated into a scheduled pipeline to enable daily computation of travel demand based on updated mobility data.

3.2.9 Safe routing engine

3.2.9.1 Component overview

The purpose of the safe routing engine is to generate paths for various types of VRUs based on requests that include an origin and a destination point. The operation of the routing engine is underpinned by the representation of a street network using nodes (representing intersections) and edges (representing road sections). Risk factors allocated to each network element are being utilised for the generation of the safety route. Furthermore, a detour factor, set by the user, enables the generation of various paths that combine the risk and detour factors, providing the user with multiple options.

3.2.9.2 Design

The safe routing engine is composed of the following modules:

- **Labelled graph reader:** a REST API component that retrieves the edges and nodes from the labelled graph and stores them on a local MongoDB database for faster processing.
- **Routable graph generator:** a module that converts the labelled graph data into a graph data structure with embedded routing information.
- **Routing optimiser:** a module that combines the detour and risk factors of the network for the generation of routes that range from the shortest to the safest.
- **Route generator:** a module that utilises shortest-path algorithms for the generation of point-to-point routes.

3.2.9.3 Interfaces

Table 47: Interfaces of safe routing engine

Interface #	Source component	Destination component	Interface type
Int9.1	Labelled graph	Safe routing engine	JSON
Int9.2	User information services	Safe routing engine	JSON
Int9.3	Safe routing engine	User information services	JSON

Table 48: Summary of Int9.1 (Labelled graph to safe routing engine)

<p>Data description</p>	<p>The network representation with weights for safe and clean routing</p>
<p>Data model / sample</p>	<p>Node representation</p> <pre>{ "type": "Feature", "geometry": { "type": "Point", "coordinates": [-3.6844432000000005, 40.4212466] }, "properties": { "ID": 0, "osmid_original": 171946, "version": "1.0", "date": "2024-06-26", "accident_risk": 3, "accident_risk_pedestrians": 3, "accident_risk_cyclists": 4 } }</pre> <p>Edge representation</p> <pre>{ "type": "Feature", "geometry": { "type": "LineString", "coordinates": [[-3.6844432000000005, 40.4212466], [...]] }, "properties": { "u": 0, "v": 1, "key": 0, "version": "1.0", "date": "2024-06-26", "processedEdgeData": { "osmid": 807334397, "oneway": true, "length": 43.958718814947446, "geometry": { "type": "LineString", "coordinates": [[-3.6844432000000005, 40.4212466], [...]] } }, "roadType": "tertiary", "numberOfLanes": 4, "width": 14, "surfaceType": "asphalt" }, "processedSegmentData": { "subedges": [</pre>

```

[
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  40.4212466
], [...]
],
"segmentsBBox": [
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    [
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      40.42125787603395
    ], [...]
    [
      -3.684632229164637,
      40.42144651976394
    ], [...]
  ]
],
"segmentDistances": [
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  22.959635803649537
],
"trafficLights": [
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  0
],
"stopYieldSignal": 0,
"pedestrianCrossings": [
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],
"cycllingPath": [
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  0
],
"pTStop": 0,
"pTPriority": [
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  0
],
"cycleParking": [
  0,
  0
],
"parkingLeft": [
  0,
  0
],
"parkingRight": [
  0,
  0
],
"drivingBarrier": 0,
"schoolNearBy": 0,
"hospitalNearBy": 0,
"maxSpeed": 50,
"zonalSpeed": [
  0,
  0
],
"tramTracks": 0
}
}

```

Data format	JSON
Security requirements	
Invocation frequency	Upon start-up of the component

Table 49: Summary of Int9.2 (User information services to safe routing engine)

Data description	Routing request received by the SOTERIA mobile application
Data model / sample	<pre>{ "uid": "12345678", "detour": 12, "localtime": "2011-11-04 00:05:23.283+00:00", "origin": { "lat": 37.978304, "lng": 23.750381 }, "destination": { "lat": 37.984934, "lng": 23.739910 } }</pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	
Invocation frequency	Upon user input

Table 50: Summary of Int9.3 (Safe routing engine to user information services)

Data description	Routing response generated by the engine and sent to the SOTERIA mobile application
Data model / sample	<pre>{ "modes": ["walking"], "travelTime": 1563, "distance": 1527, "api": "Here", "localStartTime": "2024-10-25T10:09:56+0200", "startTime": 1729843797, "type": "safest", "legs": [{ "isPT": false, "id": "oi2jhg0ngaqv6gq65of048", "distance": 1527, "travelTime": 1563, "mode": "walking", }] }</pre>

	<pre> "startTime": 1729843797, "waitingTime": 0, "steps": [{ "distance": 1527, "travelTime": 1563, "points": [[13.7288515, 51.0440886], [...]] }], "localStartTime": "2024-10-25T10:09:57+0200", "origin": [13.7288515, 51.0440886], "destination": [13.7336599, 51.0339] } }, "origin": [13.728619, 51.043876], "destination": [13.733597, 51.033622], "ptRoute": true, "id": "ri81uo0muhus0gc10rgpi" } </pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	
Invocation frequency	Upon user input

3.2.9.4 Interface specifications

Int9.1: Labelled graph with safe routing engine

This interface allows the transfer of labelled graph data to the safe routing engine. The labelled graph data is received through two dedicated endpoints: one for the nodes and another for the edges of the network. The returned network elements are formatted in geoJSON, with nodes represented as geoJSON Points and edges represented as geoJSON LineStrings. Additionally, metadata about these elements, including risk factors, is provided as 'properties' within the JSON format.

Int9.2: User information services with safe routing engine

This interface enables users to generate routing requests through the SOTERIA mobile app. The request contains data related to the origin and destination of the trip, the time of the trip and the detour factor preferred by the user.

Int9.3: Safe routing engine with user information services

This interface encompasses the routes generated by the safe routing engine upon the receipt of a user request. Each route is split into a series of ‘legs’ and ‘steps’. A leg is a part of a trip that can be performed with a specific mode, and it is divided into several steps. The response includes route metadata in the form of length, travel time and type (i.e. fastest, safest, etc.).

3.2.9.5 Deployment approach

The safe routing engine has been deployed as a containerised application (Docker) and is being hosted on a UOW-owned machine.

3.2.9.6 Testing

Table 51. Results of testing the safe routing engine

Description	Result
Unit testing was adopted to ensure the functioning of the three interfaces.	Achieved

3.2.9.7 Non-functional requirements

Table 52. Non-functional requirements for the safe routing engine

Availability	The component must be operational at all times.
Capacity	The component should provide a safe route option triggered by the input of start-/ending point and road user type.
Latency	~ 3s.
Monitoring	The availability of the component must be monitored by requests every 5 minutes. Down times of the service should be logged.
Extensibility	The first algorithms will be based on cyclists and pedestrians. Later algorithms shall hold more profiles for other road user types (e.g., e-scooter). Further possible extensions could be in other spatial areas apart from the LLs.
Portability	The solution can be portable to all the LLs.

3.2.10 Micro-vehicle sensor kit

3.2.10.1 Component overview

The micro-vehicle sensor kit will equip various types of vehicles with smart sensors and cameras and offer additional functionality to VRUs about safe speed limits, potential hazards, near-miss data, bike-handling data, air-quality data, potholes, obstacle proximity data, personal fitness trackers, unclear guided ways, and situational-aware warnings. For instance, sensors such as accelerometers, gyroscopes and magnetometers that enable direct measurement of vibrations and movement of rotary devices. Data acquired from different sources can then be aggregated and provide better insights into VRUs and urban decision makers. A dynamic safe mobility sensor kit will integrate data from various static and dynamic sources and will allow visualisations of diagnostic and prognostic safety assessment indicators in the context of ‘live’ risk hotspots and micro-mobility hazard maps. Similarly, the vehicle handling sensors will gather various parameters of sensor data such as position, speed, vibration, environment about everyday bicycle use. This data will support decision makers in traffic planning in their work and make a positive contribution to optimising the bicycle infrastructure. The position and acceleration sensors provide information about the roughness of the cycle paths. In addition, equipping citizens' bicycles with sensors enables new insights into the condition of the bicycle infrastructure and everyday use of bicycles. Environmental data such as air pressure, temperature, humidity and brightness are gathered by the sensor to be able to determine to what extent environmental factors influence cycling behaviour.

3.2.10.2 Design

Figure 19: Micro-vehicle sensor kit description diagram

3.2.10.3 Interfaces

Table 53. Interfaces of micro-vehicle sensor kit

Interface #	Source component	Destination component	Interface type
Int10.1	Micro-vehicle sensor kit	External consumer (web user interface)	File transfer
Int10.2	Micro-vehicle sensor kit	Safe mobility data space	File transfer

Table 54. Summary of Int10.1 (Micro-vehicle sensor kit to external consumer)

Data description	Data collected by the different sensors and devices integrated in the micro-vehicle sensor kit (excluding camera footage)																																																
Data model / sample	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2">Timestamp</th> <th>Temperature</th> <th>Humidity</th> <th>Pressure</th> <th>Ax</th> <th>Ay</th> <th>Az</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td colspan="2">2025-01-13T12:15:39.398Z</td> <td>20.07999992</td> <td>37</td> <td>1018.071594</td> <td>-1177</td> <td>-465</td> <td>3872</td> </tr> <tr> <th>Gx</th> <th>Gy</th> <th>Gz</th> <th>Qx</th> <th>Qy</th> <th>Qz</th> <th colspan="2">Qw</th> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>-1</td> <td>1</td> <td>-0.031799234</td> <td>0.153014749</td> <td>-0.175902873</td> <td colspan="2">0.97186029</td> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="2">F1</th> <th>F2</th> <th>DisL</th> <th>DisH</th> <th>DisR</th> <th>lat</th> <th>lon</th> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2">0.818883181</td> <td>18.35454559</td> <td>5.89</td> <td>8</td> <td>3.72</td> <td>52.485455</td> <td>-1.795382</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Timestamp		Temperature	Humidity	Pressure	Ax	Ay	Az	2025-01-13T12:15:39.398Z		20.07999992	37	1018.071594	-1177	-465	3872	Gx	Gy	Gz	Qx	Qy	Qz	Qw		0	-1	1	-0.031799234	0.153014749	-0.175902873	0.97186029		F1		F2	DisL	DisH	DisR	lat	lon	0.818883181		18.35454559	5.89	8	3.72	52.485455	-1.795382
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Data format	CSV files																																																
Security requirements	Non-encrypted data transfer																																																
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests																																																

Table 55. Summary of Int10.2 (Micro-vehicle sensor kit to safe mobility data space)

Data description	Data collected by the different sensors and devices integrated in the micro-vehicle sensor kit																																																
Data model / sample	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2">Timestamp</th> <th>Temperature</th> <th>Humidity</th> <th>Pressure</th> <th>Ax</th> <th>Ay</th> <th>Az</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td colspan="2">2025-01-13T12:15:39.398Z</td> <td>20.07999992</td> <td>37</td> <td>1018.071594</td> <td>-1177</td> <td>-465</td> <td>3872</td> </tr> <tr> <th>Gx</th> <th>Gy</th> <th>Gz</th> <th>Qx</th> <th>Qy</th> <th>Qz</th> <th colspan="2">Qw</th> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>-1</td> <td>1</td> <td>-0.031799234</td> <td>0.153014749</td> <td>-0.175902873</td> <td colspan="2">0.97186029</td> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="2">F1</th> <th>F2</th> <th>DisL</th> <th>DisH</th> <th>DisR</th> <th>lat</th> <th>lon</th> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2">0.818883181</td> <td>18.35454559</td> <td>5.89</td> <td>8</td> <td>3.72</td> <td>52.485455</td> <td>-1.795382</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Timestamp		Temperature	Humidity	Pressure	Ax	Ay	Az	2025-01-13T12:15:39.398Z		20.07999992	37	1018.071594	-1177	-465	3872	Gx	Gy	Gz	Qx	Qy	Qz	Qw		0	-1	1	-0.031799234	0.153014749	-0.175902873	0.97186029		F1		F2	DisL	DisH	DisR	lat	lon	0.818883181		18.35454559	5.89	8	3.72	52.485455	-1.795382
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F1		F2	DisL	DisH	DisR	lat	lon																																										
0.818883181		18.35454559	5.89	8	3.72	52.485455	-1.795382																																										
Data format	CSV & MP4 files																																																
Security requirements	Non-encrypted data transfer																																																
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests																																																

3.2.10.3.1 Interface specifications

Int10.1: Micro-vehicle sensor kit with external consumer (web user interface)

Micro-level data about micro-mobility collected by the micro-vehicle sensor kit is stored either locally (Secure Digital (SD) card) or in the cloud as CSV files. This data includes the readings and measurements of all integrated sensors and devices in the micro-vehicle sensor kit except video footage. The developed web user interface reads these files, shows the embedded data and visualise the related signals so the micro-mobility user gets better understanding about the micro-vehicle status and the surrounding situations.

Int10.2: Micro-vehicle sensor kit with safe mobility data space

Micro-level data about micro-mobility collected by the micro-vehicle sensor kit can be stored locally or in the cloud as CSV files. Additionally, this data will be stored in the SMDS as CSV and MP4 files. This data includes the readings and measurements of all integrated sensors and devices in the micro-vehicle sensor kit. Therefore, this data can be accessed by other beneficiary services and components such as micro-mobility hazards mapper

3.2.10.4 Deployment approach

A local server was selected rather than relying on cloud-based services. It allows for full control over data flow, security protocols, and customisation. The sensor kit communicates directly with the server, enabling real-time monitoring and data logging without external dependencies. While this setup requires more technical expertise, it offers greater flexibility and autonomy in managing the sensor kit.

3.2.10.5 Testing

Table 56. Results of testing the micro-vehicle sensor kit

Description	Result
Unit testing has been adopted to ensure the interface with the external consumer (web UI, Int10.1).	Achieved
Unit testing will be adopted to ensure the interface with SMDS to store the output of the component (Int10.2).	Ongoing

3.2.10.6 Non-functional requirements

Table 57. Non-functional requirements for the micro-vehicle sensor kit

Availability	The sensor kit must always be operational. Non-availability of the sensor data will impact the speed advise provided to end-users and will impact the safety of VRUs.
Capacity	The sensor kit should be active and operational all the time to collect all required data in real time and store this data in the database.
Latency	The maximum acceptable time for generating sensor and video data should not be more that 60 sec.

Monitoring	The availability of the sensor kit and video data must be monitored by requests every five minutes. All requests and responses can be logged.
Extensibility	This version will support various sensor and video data sources / types.
Portability	The solution can be deployed and in all the LLs, if required.

3.2.11 Environmental sensor kit

3.2.11.1 Component overview

The environmental sensor kit can be mounted on various types of vehicles and collects data on air quality (via PM sensors), temperature, and humidity. Simultaneously, it records precise location and movement using GPS and accelerometer / gyroscope sensors. The collected data is transmitted and used to visualise pollution levels and microclimate conditions across urban areas, helping to identify pollution hotspots. Additionally, the positional and motion data supports safer use of micro-mobility vehicles and contributes to more efficient and VRU-friendly urban planning and development by providing it to urban planners and VRUs.

3.2.11.2 Design

Figure 20: Environmental sensor kit description diagram

3.2.11.3 Interfaces

Table 58. Interfaces of micro-vehicle sensor kit

Interface #	Source component	Destination component	Interface type
Int11.1	Micro-vehicle sensor kit	External consumer (Web user interface)	File transfer
Int11.2	Micro-vehicle sensor kit	Safe mobility data space	File transfer

Table 59. Summary of Int11.1 (Micro-vehicle sensor kit to external consumer)

Data description	Data collected by the different sensors and devices integrated in the micro-vehicle sensor kit
Data model / sample	<pre> {"sensor_id":"cyclosensor-ccdba72de88c","timestamp":"2024-10-27 07:51:39+00","gyro_accel":[[[1.122881,-0.593762,9.485827],[-0.02518071,0.01838591,-0.009459419]],[[1.115698,-0.6200982,9.591172]]]} {"sensor_id":"cyclosensor-ccdba72de88c","timestamp":"2024-10-27 08:03:13+00","long":38.07601,"lat":23.80584} {"sensor_id":"cyclosensor-fce8c07bc618","timestamp":"2024-10-27 02:32:00+00","temperature":19.66201,"humidity":54.64256} {"sensor_id":"cyclosensor-ccdba72eb2f0","timestamp":"2024-11-18 19:28:06+00","pm_1":10.0,"pm_2_5":10.0,"pm_10":10.0} </pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	Non-encrypted data transfer
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

Table 60. Summary of Int11.2 (Micro-vehicle sensor kit to the SMDS)

Data description	Data collected by the different sensors and devices integrated in the micro-vehicle sensor kit
Data model / sample	<pre> {"sensor_id":"cyclosensor-ccdba72de88c","timestamp":"2024-10-27 07:51:39+00","gyro_accel":[[[1.122881,-0.593762,9.485827],[-0.02518071,0.01838591,-0.009459419]],[[1.115698,-0.6200982,9.591172]]]} {"sensor_id":"cyclosensor-ccdba72de88c","timestamp":"2024-10-27 08:03:13+00","long":38.07601,"lat":23.80584} {"sensor_id":"cyclosensor-fce8c07bc618","timestamp":"2024-10-27 02:32:00+00","temperature":19.66201,"humidity":54.64256} {"sensor_id":"cyclosensor-ccdba72eb2f0","timestamp":"2024-11-18 19:28:06+00","pm_1":10.0,"pm_2_5":10.0,"pm_10":10.0} </pre>

Data format	JSON
Security requirements	Non-encrypted data transfer
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

3.2.11.3.1 Interface specifications

Int11.1: Micro-vehicle sensor kit with external consumer (web user interface)

Micro-level data about micro-mobility collected by the environmental sensor kit is stored on a SD card. This data includes the readings and measurements of all integrated sensors. The developed web user interface reads these files, shows the embedded data and visualises the related signals so that the micro-mobility user gets a better understanding of the micro-vehicle status and the surrounding situation.

Int11.2: Micro-vehicle sensor kit with SMDS

Micro-level data about micro-mobility collected by the micro-vehicle sensor kit can be stored locally or in the cloud as CSV files. Additionally, this data will be stored in the SMDS as CSV files and MP4 files. This data includes the readings and measurements of all integrated sensors and devices in the environmental sensor kit. Therefore, this data can be accessed by other beneficiary services and components such as micro-mobility accident and pollution hotspots.

3.2.11.4 Deployment approach

A local server was selected rather than relying on cloud-based services for full control over data flow, security protocols, and customisation. The sensor kit communicates directly with the server, enabling real-time monitoring and data logging without external dependencies.

3.2.11.5 Testing

Table 61. Results of testing the environmental sensor kit

Description	Result
Unit testing has been adopted to ensure the functioning of the interface with the external consumer (web user interface, Int11.1).	Achieved
Unit testing will be adopted to ensure the functioning of the interface with the SMDS to store the output of the component (Int11.2).	Achieved

3.2.11.6 Non-functional requirements

Table 62. Non-functional requirements for the environmental sensor kit

Availability	The environmental sensor kit must always be operational.
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Capacity	The environmental sensor kit should be active and operational at all times to collect all required data in real time and store it in the database.
Latency	
Monitoring	
Extensibility	The current version supports various sensors.
Portability	The solution can be deployed and tested in all the SOTERIA LLs, if required.

3.2.12 Micro-mobility hazards mapper

3.2.12.1 Component overview

The micro-mobility hazards mapper is a data-driven service that will support users of micro-mobility to minimise risks that may lead to accidents. It uses micro-level data collected by VRUs to identify potential hazards that may destabilise micro-vehicles or accumulatively lead to a potential accident. Essentially, it identifies and highlights areas with specific infrastructure deficiencies (e.g. potholes, unclear guided ways, etc.) and a high number of vehicle conflicts (i.e. complex intersections) and then it proactively notifies VRUs of such potential hazards. Therefore, this component provides real time hazard hotspots to be considered by VRUs, minimises errors in their decision making and avoids exposure to hazardous situations.

3.2.12.2 Design

Figure 21: Micro-mobility hazards mapper description diagram

3.2.12.3 Interfaces

Table 63. Interfaces of micro-mobility hazards mapper

Interface #	Source component	Destination component	Interface type
Int12.1	SMDS	Micro-mobility hazards mapper	File transfer
Int12.2	External provider (i.e. CycleStreets API)	Micro-mobility hazards mapper	Rest API or file transfer
Int12.3	External provider (i.e. OSM)	Micro-mobility hazards mapper	File transfer
Int12.4	Micro-mobility hazards mapper	SMDS	File transfer

Table 64. Summary of Int12.1 (Safe mobility data space to micro-mobility hazards mapper)

Data description	Micro-level data on micro-mobility collected by VRUs (micro-vehicle sensor kit data)																																																
Data model / sample	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2">Timestamp</th> <th>Temperature</th> <th>Humidity</th> <th>Pressure</th> <th>Ax</th> <th>Ay</th> <th>Az</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td colspan="2">2025-01-13T12:15:39.398Z</td> <td>20.07999992</td> <td>37</td> <td>1018.071594</td> <td>-1177</td> <td>-465</td> <td>3872</td> </tr> <tr> <th>Gx</th> <th>Gy</th> <th>Gz</th> <th>Qx</th> <th>Qy</th> <th>Qz</th> <th colspan="2">Qw</th> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>-1</td> <td>1</td> <td>-0.031799234</td> <td>0.153014749</td> <td>-0.175902873</td> <td colspan="2">0.97186029</td> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="2">F1</th> <th>F2</th> <th>DisL</th> <th>DisH</th> <th>DisR</th> <th>lat</th> <th>lon</th> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2">0.818883181</td> <td>18.35454559</td> <td>5.89</td> <td>8</td> <td>3.72</td> <td>52.485455</td> <td>-1.795382</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Timestamp		Temperature	Humidity	Pressure	Ax	Ay	Az	2025-01-13T12:15:39.398Z		20.07999992	37	1018.071594	-1177	-465	3872	Gx	Gy	Gz	Qx	Qy	Qz	Qw		0	-1	1	-0.031799234	0.153014749	-0.175902873	0.97186029		F1		F2	DisL	DisH	DisR	lat	lon	0.818883181		18.35454559	5.89	8	3.72	52.485455	-1.795382
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Data format	CSV file																																																
Security requirements	Non-encrypted data transfer																																																
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests																																																

Table 65. Summary of Int12.2 (External provider to micro-mobility hazards mapper)

Data description	Road / traffic accident data (location, severity and injuries)																																																																																							
Data model / sample	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Key</th> <th>Value</th> <th>Type</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>▼ (1) {_id : 6825a42b753b406f4484f478}</td> <td>{ 33 fields }</td> <td>Document</td> </tr> <tr> <td> _id</td> <td>6825a42b753b406f4484f478</td> <td>ObjectId</td> </tr> <tr> <td> id</td> <td>199943P008099</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> casualties</td> <td>Car occupant</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> year</td> <td>1999</td> <td>Int32</td> </tr> <tr> <td> longitude</td> <td>-1.297642</td> <td>Double</td> </tr> <tr> <td> latitude</td> <td>51.78112</td> <td>Double</td> </tr> <tr> <td> severity</td> <td>Slight</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> num_vehicles</td> <td>2</td> <td>Int32</td> </tr> <tr> <td> num_casualties</td> <td>1</td> <td>Int32</td> </tr> <tr> <td> date</td> <td>936140400.0</td> <td>Double</td> </tr> <tr> <td> datetime</td> <td>936210300</td> <td>Int32</td> </tr> <tr> <td> 1st_road_class</td> <td>C</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> road_type</td> <td>Single carriageway</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> speed_limit</td> <td>30</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> junction_detail</td> <td>Private drive or entrance</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> pedestrian_cross</td> <td>No physical crossing facilities within 50 metres</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> light_conditions</td> <td>Daylight</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> weather_conditions</td> <td>Fine no high winds</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> surface_conditions</td> <td>Dry</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> special_conditions</td> <td>None</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> crgway_hazards</td> <td>None</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> > vehicle_type</td> <td>[2 elements]</td> <td>Array</td> </tr> <tr> <td> > vehicle_location</td> <td>[2 elements]</td> <td>Array</td> </tr> <tr> <td> > casualty_class</td> <td>[1 elements]</td> <td>Array</td> </tr> <tr> <td> > casualty_severity</td> <td>[1 elements]</td> <td>Array</td> </tr> <tr> <td> > pedestrian_location</td> <td>[1 elements]</td> <td>Array</td> </tr> <tr> <td> > casualty_type</td> <td>[1 elements]</td> <td>Array</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Key	Value	Type	▼ (1) {_id : 6825a42b753b406f4484f478}	{ 33 fields }	Document	_id	6825a42b753b406f4484f478	ObjectId	id	199943P008099	String	casualties	Car occupant	String	year	1999	Int32	longitude	-1.297642	Double	latitude	51.78112	Double	severity	Slight	String	num_vehicles	2	Int32	num_casualties	1	Int32	date	936140400.0	Double	datetime	936210300	Int32	1st_road_class	C	String	road_type	Single carriageway	String	speed_limit	30	String	junction_detail	Private drive or entrance	String	pedestrian_cross	No physical crossing facilities within 50 metres	String	light_conditions	Daylight	String	weather_conditions	Fine no high winds	String	surface_conditions	Dry	String	special_conditions	None	String	crgway_hazards	None	String	> vehicle_type	[2 elements]	Array	> vehicle_location	[2 elements]	Array	> casualty_class	[1 elements]	Array	> casualty_severity	[1 elements]	Array	> pedestrian_location	[1 elements]	Array	> casualty_type	[1 elements]	Array
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year	1999	Int32																																																																																						
longitude	-1.297642	Double																																																																																						
latitude	51.78112	Double																																																																																						
severity	Slight	String																																																																																						
num_vehicles	2	Int32																																																																																						
num_casualties	1	Int32																																																																																						
date	936140400.0	Double																																																																																						
datetime	936210300	Int32																																																																																						
1st_road_class	C	String																																																																																						
road_type	Single carriageway	String																																																																																						
speed_limit	30	String																																																																																						
junction_detail	Private drive or entrance	String																																																																																						
pedestrian_cross	No physical crossing facilities within 50 metres	String																																																																																						
light_conditions	Daylight	String																																																																																						
weather_conditions	Fine no high winds	String																																																																																						
surface_conditions	Dry	String																																																																																						
special_conditions	None	String																																																																																						
crgway_hazards	None	String																																																																																						
> vehicle_type	[2 elements]	Array																																																																																						
> vehicle_location	[2 elements]	Array																																																																																						
> casualty_class	[1 elements]	Array																																																																																						
> casualty_severity	[1 elements]	Array																																																																																						
> pedestrian_location	[1 elements]	Array																																																																																						
> casualty_type	[1 elements]	Array																																																																																						
Data format	JSON																																																																																							
Security requirements	Non-encrypted data transfer																																																																																							
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests																																																																																							

Table 66. Summary of Int12.3 (External provider to micro-mobility hazards mapper)

Data description	Map data (road category, maximum speed, lightening and surface type)		
Data model / sample	Key	Value	Type
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ (1) {_id : 681a189b753b403ac89fde08} _id way_id nodes tags <ul style="list-style-type: none"> highway maxspeed name 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> { 4 fields } 681a189b753b403ac89fde08 1204 [6 elements] { 3 fields } residential 20 mph Brogden Close 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Document ObjectId String Array Object String String String
Data format	JSON		
Security requirements	Non-encrypted data transfer		
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests		

Table 67. Summary of Int12.4 (Micro-mobility hazards mapper to safe mobility data space)

Data description	Micro-mobility hazards map (hazards location, type and severity)		
Data model / sample	Key	Value	Type
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ (1) {_id : 682c5b84753b401c10b812c5} _id osmway_id location <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0 1 hazard_probability expected_injury affected_users hazard_severity affected_vehicles road_class road_maxSpeed possible_cause hazard_type osm_roadType osm_roadSurface osm_roadLight 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> { 15 fields } 682c5b84753b401c10b812c5 60257052-1 [2 elements] -1.2885567 51.7899054 Low Serious VRU Low Microvehicle A 60 Visibility and Weather Road_Infrastructure Special Paved No 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Document ObjectId String Array Double Double String
Data format	JSON		
Security requirements	Non-encrypted data transfer		
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests		

3.2.12.3.1 Interface specifications

Int12.1: SMDS with micro-mobility hazards mapper

Micro-level data on micro-mobility collected by micro-mobility users or VRUs using the micro-vehicle sensor kit will be stored in the safe mobility data space as CSV files. This data includes the readings and measurements of all integrated sensors and devices in the micro-vehicle sensor kit. First, the majority of this collected data will be obtained to train several hazards detection machine learning models. Then, this data can be accessed on a regular basis (depending on the availability of real time data) to update the hazard map.

Int12.2: External provider with micro-mobility hazards mapper

In case the micro-vehicle sensor kit data is not available, historical accident and injury data can be obtained from external providers such as CycleStreets API for the Oxfordshire area. So, this data can be extracted as JSON files from available sources and saved in a local database to be used in this component.

Int12.3: External provider with micro-mobility hazards mapper

In case the micro-vehicle sensor kit data is not available, additional data can be obtained from external providers such as OpenStreetMap to enhance the data collected about historical accidents and injury. This data includes the maximum speed, type and category of road and it can be extracted as JSON files for the study area and saved in a local database to be used in this component.

Int12.4: Micro-mobility hazards mapper with SMDS

As a result of implementing the component, the generated (or updated) micro-mobility hazards map will be exported and saved in the micro-mobility data space as JSON files. These results mainly includes the location (i.e. coordinates), hazard type and severity.

3.2.12.4 Deployment approach

A local server was selected rather than relying on cloud-based services for full control over data flow from the sensor kit to the micro-mobility hazards mapper without external dependencies.

3.2.12.5 Testing

Table 68. Results of testing the micro-mobility hazard mapper

Description	Result
Sample payloads were created to test the responses from the API endpoints and websites and specifically, CycleStreets API to collect accident data in Oxfordshire area.	Achieved
Unit testing will be adopted to ensure the following interfaces: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ interface with the SMDS to get the data collected by the micro-vehicle sensor kit data ▪ interface with OpenStreetMap to collect road data ▪ interface with the SMDS to store the output of the component. 	Ongoing

3.2.12.6 Non-functional requirements

Table 69. Non-functional requirements for the micro-mobility hazards mapper

Availability	The component must always be operational. Non-availability of the component may impact the speed advise provided to end-users and may impact the safety of VRUs.
Capacity	The component can provide a hazards map based on real time data collected from micro-vehicles and micro-mobility users. The component may be triggered every five minutes to update the hazards map and store it in the database so it can be accessed by other components. Alternatively, a static hazards map can be provided if real time data is not available.
Latency	The maximum acceptable time for generating / updating the hazards map should not be more tha 60 sec.
Monitoring	The availability of the component can be monitored by requests every five minutes. All requests and responses can be logged.
Extensibility	The component will support various data sources / types and micro-mobility users (e.g. cyclists). However, additional data sources and other types of micro-mobility users (e.g. e-scooter riders) may be integrated in the future.
Portability	The solution can be deployed and implemented (may be with some minor amendments related to the input data) in all the LLs, if input data is available.

3.2.13 Protective equipment assessment module

3.2.13.1 Component overview

Protective equipment aims to enhance micro-mobility safety, promotes sustainable micro-mobility and reduces traffic accidents which involve VRUs. Effectively, protective equipment assessment module is a data-driven service that will evaluate the effectiveness of various types of protective equipment (i.e. helmet, reflectors, protective glasses, etc.) used by VRUs according to the status of the network (i.e. traffic density), environmental conditions (i.e. weather, level of visibility, etc.) and characteristics of the VRUs (i.e. behaviour, physical condition, etc.). This module correlates metrics related to the surroundings of a micro-vehicle with characteristics and features of protective equipment used by their driver for assessing their effectiveness.

3.2.13.2 Design

Figure 22: Protective equipment assessment module description diagram

3.2.13.3 Interfaces

Table 70. Interfaces of protective equipment assessment module

Interface #	Source component	Destination component	Interface type
Int13.1	Micro-vehicle sensor kit	Protective equipment assessment module	File transfer
Int13.2	External provider (i.e. micro-mobility users)	Protective equipment assessment module	File transfer
Int13.3	Protective equipment assessment module	SMDS	File transfer

Table 71. Summary of Int13.1 (Micro-vehicle sensor kit to protective equipment assessment module)

Data description	Characteristics of micro-mobility users (VRUs), road traffic incidents and accidents (near misses and collisions)
-------------------------	---

Data model / sample	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Key</th> <th>Value</th> <th>Type</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>√ (X) (1) {_id : 682c5b84753b401c10b812c5}</td> <td>{ 15 fields }</td> <td>Document</td> </tr> <tr> <td> _id</td> <td>682c5b84753b401c10b812c5</td> <td>ObjectId</td> </tr> <tr> <td> osmway_id</td> <td>60257052-1</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> √ [3] location</td> <td>[2 elements]</td> <td>Array</td> </tr> <tr> <td> 0</td> <td>-1.2885567</td> <td>Double</td> </tr> <tr> <td> 1</td> <td>51.7899054</td> <td>Double</td> </tr> <tr> <td> hazard_probability</td> <td>Low</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> expected_injury</td> <td>Serious</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> affected_users</td> <td>VRU</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> hazard_severity</td> <td>Low</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> affected_vehicles</td> <td>Microvehicle</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> road_class</td> <td>A</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> road_maxSpeed</td> <td>60</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> possible_cause</td> <td>Visibility and Weather</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> hazard_type</td> <td>Road_Infrastructure</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> osm_roadType</td> <td>Special</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> osm_roadSurface</td> <td>Paved</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> osm_roadLight</td> <td>No</td> <td>String</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Key	Value	Type	√ (X) (1) {_id : 682c5b84753b401c10b812c5}	{ 15 fields }	Document	_id	682c5b84753b401c10b812c5	ObjectId	osmway_id	60257052-1	String	√ [3] location	[2 elements]	Array	0	-1.2885567	Double	1	51.7899054	Double	hazard_probability	Low	String	expected_injury	Serious	String	affected_users	VRU	String	hazard_severity	Low	String	affected_vehicles	Microvehicle	String	road_class	A	String	road_maxSpeed	60	String	possible_cause	Visibility and Weather	String	hazard_type	Road_Infrastructure	String	osm_roadType	Special	String	osm_roadSurface	Paved	String	osm_roadLight	No	String
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expected_injury	Serious	String																																																								
affected_users	VRU	String																																																								
hazard_severity	Low	String																																																								
affected_vehicles	Microvehicle	String																																																								
road_class	A	String																																																								
road_maxSpeed	60	String																																																								
possible_cause	Visibility and Weather	String																																																								
hazard_type	Road_Infrastructure	String																																																								
osm_roadType	Special	String																																																								
osm_roadSurface	Paved	String																																																								
osm_roadLight	No	String																																																								
Data format	Video clips (MP4 file) or JSON file																																																									
Security requirements	Non-encrypted data transfer																																																									
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests																																																									

Table 72. Summary of Int13.2 (External provider to protective equipment assessment module)

Data description	Characteristics of used protective equipment, micro-mobility user behaviour, previously experienced accidents and injuries																																																												
Data model / sample	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Timestamp</th> <th>REBO camera ID</th> <th>Q1. Which type of micromobility or vulnerable road user do you represent?</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>06/09/2025 12:19</td> <td>99999</td> <td>E-scooter</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Q2. When you use your micromobility, you do the following (select ALL that apply):</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Kerb-jump on the pavement to avoid slowing or stopping, Weave between other vehicles or users to avoid slowing or stopping,</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Q3. When you are traveling, which of the following tools or equipment do you use? (select ALL that apply):</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">High visibility clothing (e.g. illuminous coat), Front light, Bell or horn</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Q4. When you are traveling, which of the following protective equipment (PE) do you wear? (select ALL that apply):</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Helmet, Glasses, mask or shield</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Q5. While using micromobility mode of transportation, have you been involved in an accident (e.g. crash) or about to</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Fall down</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Q6. In case you've been involved in an accident (i.e. crash or fall down), which part(s) of your body did you sustain injury</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Arms, Legs</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Q7. In case you've been involved in a "crash" or "fall down" incident and sustained injury, how would you describe the severity</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Moderate injury (e.g. orthopaedic)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Q8. In case you've been involved in an accident or about to be involved in an accident, who is responsible or what</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">None of the above (i.e. other reasons)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Q9. Using the following tools or equipment has prevented the occurrence of an accident and/or reduced the severity</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">None of the above (i.e. the effectiveness of the used PE has not been recognised)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">Q10. Wearing the following protective equipment (PE) has mitigated the impacts of an occurred accident (e.g. crash</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="3">None of the above (i.e. the effectiveness of the used PE has not been recognised)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Timestamp	REBO camera ID	Q1. Which type of micromobility or vulnerable road user do you represent?	06/09/2025 12:19	99999	E-scooter	Q2. When you use your micromobility, you do the following (select ALL that apply):			Kerb-jump on the pavement to avoid slowing or stopping, Weave between other vehicles or users to avoid slowing or stopping,			Q3. When you are traveling, which of the following tools or equipment do you use? (select ALL that apply):			High visibility clothing (e.g. illuminous coat), Front light, Bell or horn			Q4. When you are traveling, which of the following protective equipment (PE) do you wear? (select ALL that apply):			Helmet, Glasses, mask or shield			Q5. While using micromobility mode of transportation, have you been involved in an accident (e.g. crash) or about to			Fall down			Q6. In case you've been involved in an accident (i.e. crash or fall down), which part(s) of your body did you sustain injury			Arms, Legs			Q7. In case you've been involved in a "crash" or "fall down" incident and sustained injury, how would you describe the severity			Moderate injury (e.g. orthopaedic)			Q8. In case you've been involved in an accident or about to be involved in an accident, who is responsible or what			None of the above (i.e. other reasons)			Q9. Using the following tools or equipment has prevented the occurrence of an accident and/or reduced the severity			None of the above (i.e. the effectiveness of the used PE has not been recognised)			Q10. Wearing the following protective equipment (PE) has mitigated the impacts of an occurred accident (e.g. crash			None of the above (i.e. the effectiveness of the used PE has not been recognised)		
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Data format	CSV file																																																												

Security requirements	Non-encrypted data transfer
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests

Table 73. Summary of Int13.3 (Protective equipment assessment module to SMDS)

Data description	The effectiveness of micro-mobility protective equipment																																																																																																											
Data model / sample	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">sustained_injury</th> <th>Head</th> <th>Face</th> <th>Chest</th> <th>Back</th> <th>Arms</th> <th>Hands</th> <th>Legs</th> <th>Feet</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">used_PE</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">Helmet</td> <td>28</td> <td>33</td> <td>18</td> <td>36</td> <td>23</td> <td>31</td> <td>26</td> <td>20</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">Gloves</td> <td>38</td> <td>32</td> <td>18</td> <td>38</td> <td>31</td> <td>21</td> <td>24</td> <td>23</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">Glasses</td> <td>27.66</td> <td>38.3</td> <td>19.15</td> <td>42.55</td> <td>31.91</td> <td>25.53</td> <td>31.91</td> <td>21.28</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">Body_Armour</td> <td>30.23</td> <td>39.53</td> <td>20.93</td> <td>30.23</td> <td>16.28</td> <td>32.56</td> <td>27.91</td> <td>18.6</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">Chest_Guard</td> <td>26.83</td> <td>19.51</td> <td>31.71</td> <td>36.59</td> <td>41.46</td> <td>24.39</td> <td>19.51</td> <td>17.07</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">Back_Protector</td> <td>24.59</td> <td>27.87</td> <td>19.67</td> <td>49.18</td> <td>27.87</td> <td>31.15</td> <td>24.59</td> <td>21.31</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">Elbow_Pads</td> <td>33.33</td> <td>34.72</td> <td>16.67</td> <td>38.89</td> <td>20.83</td> <td>33.33</td> <td>20.83</td> <td>18.06</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">Knee_Pads</td> <td>34.38</td> <td>37.5</td> <td>14.06</td> <td>37.5</td> <td>26.56</td> <td>21.88</td> <td>29.69</td> <td>17.19</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="background-color: #d3d3d3;">Foot_Protector</td> <td>27.27</td> <td>39.39</td> <td>18.18</td> <td>45.45</td> <td>30.3</td> <td>27.27</td> <td>21.21</td> <td>24.24</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>									sustained_injury	Head	Face	Chest	Back	Arms	Hands	Legs	Feet	used_PE									Helmet	28	33	18	36	23	31	26	20	Gloves	38	32	18	38	31	21	24	23	Glasses	27.66	38.3	19.15	42.55	31.91	25.53	31.91	21.28	Body_Armour	30.23	39.53	20.93	30.23	16.28	32.56	27.91	18.6	Chest_Guard	26.83	19.51	31.71	36.59	41.46	24.39	19.51	17.07	Back_Protector	24.59	27.87	19.67	49.18	27.87	31.15	24.59	21.31	Elbow_Pads	33.33	34.72	16.67	38.89	20.83	33.33	20.83	18.06	Knee_Pads	34.38	37.5	14.06	37.5	26.56	21.88	29.69	17.19	Foot_Protector	27.27	39.39	18.18	45.45	30.3	27.27	21.21	24.24
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Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests																																																																																																											

3.2.13.3.1 Interface specifications

Int13.1: Micro-vehicle sensor kit to protective equipment assessment module

This component may use micro-vehicle sensor kit data and micro-mobility hazards mapper output (i.e. number of dangerous overtakes). This data can be obtained as CSV files and saved in a local database. Alternatively, micro-vehicle sensor kit data collected by cameras may be used. Effectively, this data can be saved in a local database as MP4 files (video footage for analysing and extracting near-miss data) or CSV files (extracted near-miss data). However, all this data will be obtained after the data collection process is finalised and the data from all micro-vehicle sensor kits is collected.

Int13.2: External provider (i.e. micro-mobility users) with protective equipment assessment module

In addition to the micro-vehicle sensor kit data, the component requires data about the characteristics of used protective equipment, micro-mobility user behaviour, previously

experienced accidents and injuries. This data can be obtained and collected from external data sources such as web-based questionnaires. Therefore, these questionnaire responses will be gathered from the users of the micro-vehicle sensor kit and saved as CSV files in a local database.

Int13.3: Protective equipment assessment module with safe mobility data space

As a result of implementing the component, the effectiveness evaluation of protective equipment will be saved in the micro-mobility data space as CSV files. This result mainly includes the type of protective equipment (e.g. helmet) and its effectiveness from various perspectives.

3.2.13.4 Deployment approach

A local server was selected rather than relying on cloud-based services for full control over data flow from the sensor kit, the micro-mobility hazards mapper and other data sources to the protective equipment assessment module without external dependencies.

3.2.13.5 Testing

Table 74. Results of testing the protective equipment assessment module

Description	Result
<p>Unit testing will be adopted to ensure the following interfaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The interface with the micro-vehicle sensor kit (and/or the micro-mobility hazards mapper) to get the data about road traffic incidents and accidents. ▪ The interface to get the responses of the micro-mobility users who will participate in the designed web-based questionnaire. ▪ The interface with the safe mobility data space to store the output of the component. 	Ongoing

3.2.13.6 Non-functional requirements

Table 75. Non-functional requirements for the protective equipment assessment module

Availability	The component will operate once all the required input data is collected. Non-availability of the component may impact the perception of end users about the advantages and benefits of protective equipment usage and may impact the safety of VRUs.
Capacity	The component can evaluate the effectiveness of micro-mobility protective equipment based on data collected from micro-vehicles and micro-mobility users. The component may be triggered after each round of data collection to update the assessment results and store them in the database.

Extensibility	The component will support various data sources/types and micro-mobility users. However, additional data sources and other types of micro-mobility users may be integrated in the future.
Portability	The solution can be deployed and implemented (may be with some minor amendments related to the input data) in all the LLs if input data is available.

3.2.14 Speed advisory module

3.2.14.1 Component overview

Speed advisory module is a data-driven service that will support users of micro-mobility to minimise risks that may lead to accidents. Therefore, the goal of the speed advisory module is to regulate the speed of micro-vehicles according to the road status, hazards and potential accidents. It uses the micro-level data collected from VRUs and potential hazard's locations to proactively notify and advise the users of micro-vehicles to slow down when approaching hazards. Therefore, this module is responsible for providing real-time warnings to micro-vehicles drivers about safe speed limits.

3.2.14.2 Design

Figure 23: Speed advisory module description diagram

3.2.14.3 Interfaces

Table 76. Interfaces of speed advisory module

Interface #	Source component	Destination component	Interface type
Int14.1	Micro-mobility hazards mapper	Speed advisory module	File transfer
Int14.2	Accident data processing and analysis module	Speed advisory module	Rest API or file transfer
Int14.3	External provider (i.e. OpenStreetMap)	Speed advisory module	File transfer
Int14.4	Speed advisory module	SMDS	File transfer

Table 77. Summary of Int14.1 (Micro-mobility hazards mapper to speed advisory module)

Data description	Micro-mobility hazards map (hazards location, type and severity)		
Data model / sample	<pre> Key (1) {_id: 682c5b84753b401c10b812c5} { "_id": "682c5b84753b401c10b812c5", "osmway_id": "60257052-1", "location": [{ "lat": -1.2885567, "lon": 51.7899054 }, { "lat": 51.7899054, "lon": -1.2885567 }], "hazard_probability": "Low", "expected_injury": "Serious", "affected_users": "VRU", "hazard_severity": "Low", "affected_vehicles": "Microvehicle", "road_class": "A", "road_maxSpeed": "60", "possible_cause": "Visibility and Weather", "hazard_type": "Road_Infrastructure", "osm_roadType": "Special", "osm_roadSurface": "Paved", "osm_roadLight": "No" } </pre>	Value	Type
Data format	JSON		
Security requirements	Non-encrypted data transfer		
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests		

Table 78. Summary of Int14.2 (Accident data processing and analysis module to speed advisory module)

Data description	Labelled graph data (risk data related to the edges)																																																																																													
Data model / sample	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Key</th> <th>Value</th> <th>Type</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>√ (1) {_id : 6839be3eb51aad489c70f58f}</td> <td>{ 4 fields }</td> <td>Document</td> </tr> <tr> <td> _id</td> <td>6839be3eb51aad489c70f58f</td> <td>ObjectId</td> </tr> <tr> <td> type</td> <td>Feature</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> > geometry</td> <td>{ 2 fields }</td> <td>Object</td> </tr> <tr> <td> √ properties</td> <td>{ 7 fields }</td> <td>Object</td> </tr> <tr> <td> u</td> <td>442752</td> <td>Int32</td> </tr> <tr> <td> v</td> <td>231712392</td> <td>Int32</td> </tr> <tr> <td> key</td> <td>0</td> <td>Int32</td> </tr> <tr> <td> version</td> <td>1.0</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> date</td> <td>2024-09-24</td> <td>String</td> </tr> <tr> <td> > processedEdgeData</td> <td>{ 4 fields }</td> <td>Object</td> </tr> <tr> <td> √ processedSegmentData</td> <td>{ 18 fields }</td> <td>Object</td> </tr> <tr> <td> subedges</td> <td>null</td> <td>Null</td> </tr> <tr> <td> segmentsBBox</td> <td>null</td> <td>Null</td> </tr> <tr> <td> > risk_diff_cyclist</td> <td>[1 elements]</td> <td>Array</td> </tr> <tr> <td> > risk_rel_cyclist</td> <td>[1 elements]</td> <td>Array</td> </tr> <tr> <td> > risk_score_abs_cyclist</td> <td>[1 elements]</td> <td>Array</td> </tr> <tr> <td> > risk_score_rel_cyclist</td> <td>[1 elements]</td> <td>Array</td> </tr> <tr> <td> > risk_diff_pedestrian</td> <td>[1 elements]</td> <td>Array</td> </tr> <tr> <td> > risk_rel_pedestrian</td> <td>[1 elements]</td> <td>Array</td> </tr> <tr> <td> > risk_score_abs_pedestrian</td> <td>[1 elements]</td> <td>Array</td> </tr> <tr> <td> > risk_score_rel_pedestrian</td> <td>[1 elements]</td> <td>Array</td> </tr> <tr> <td> risk_diff_cyclist_final</td> <td>-0.449448815046659</td> <td>Double</td> </tr> <tr> <td> risk_rel_cyclist_final</td> <td>-0.381048989001021</td> <td>Double</td> </tr> <tr> <td> risk_score_abs_cyclist_final</td> <td>5.0</td> <td>Double</td> </tr> <tr> <td> risk_score_rel_cyclist_final</td> <td>4.0</td> <td>Double</td> </tr> <tr> <td> risk_diff_pedestrian_final</td> <td>-0.0537468904610691</td> <td>Double</td> </tr> <tr> <td> risk_rel_pedestrian_final</td> <td>-0.051020406204722</td> <td>Double</td> </tr> <tr> <td> risk_score_abs_pedestrian_final</td> <td>5.0</td> <td>Double</td> </tr> <tr> <td> risk_score_rel_pedestrian_final</td> <td>4.0</td> <td>Double</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Key	Value	Type	√ (1) {_id : 6839be3eb51aad489c70f58f}	{ 4 fields }	Document	_id	6839be3eb51aad489c70f58f	ObjectId	type	Feature	String	> geometry	{ 2 fields }	Object	√ properties	{ 7 fields }	Object	u	442752	Int32	v	231712392	Int32	key	0	Int32	version	1.0	String	date	2024-09-24	String	> processedEdgeData	{ 4 fields }	Object	√ processedSegmentData	{ 18 fields }	Object	subedges	null	Null	segmentsBBox	null	Null	> risk_diff_cyclist	[1 elements]	Array	> risk_rel_cyclist	[1 elements]	Array	> risk_score_abs_cyclist	[1 elements]	Array	> risk_score_rel_cyclist	[1 elements]	Array	> risk_diff_pedestrian	[1 elements]	Array	> risk_rel_pedestrian	[1 elements]	Array	> risk_score_abs_pedestrian	[1 elements]	Array	> risk_score_rel_pedestrian	[1 elements]	Array	risk_diff_cyclist_final	-0.449448815046659	Double	risk_rel_cyclist_final	-0.381048989001021	Double	risk_score_abs_cyclist_final	5.0	Double	risk_score_rel_cyclist_final	4.0	Double	risk_diff_pedestrian_final	-0.0537468904610691	Double	risk_rel_pedestrian_final	-0.051020406204722	Double	risk_score_abs_pedestrian_final	5.0	Double	risk_score_rel_pedestrian_final	4.0	Double
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Security requirements	Non-encrypted data transfer																																																																																													
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests																																																																																													

Table 79. Summary of Int14.3: (External provider to speed advisory module)

Data description	Map data (road category, maximum speed, lightening and surface type)		
Data model / sample	Key	Value	Type
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ (1) {_id : 681a189b753b403ac89fde08} _id way_id nodes ▼ tags highway maxspeed name 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> { 4 fields } 681a189b753b403ac89fde08 1204 [6 elements] { 3 fields } residential 20 mph Brogden Close 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Document ObjectId String Array Object String String String
Data format	JSON		
Security requirements	Non-encrypted data transfer		
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests		

Table 80. Summary of Int14.4 (Speed advisory module to safe mobility data space)

Data description	Safe speed map (location and maximum speed limit)		
Data model / sample	Key	Value	Type
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ (1) {_id : 682f4f4a753b406d70dc89d6} _id osmway_id ▼ location 0 1 hazard_probability expected_injury hazard_severity hazard_type road_class road_maxSpeed osm_roadSurface osm_roadLight safe_speed_limit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> { 12 fields } 682f4f4a753b406d70dc89d6 474233024-1 [2 elements] -1.2811534 51.7883228 Low Slight Low Unknown A 30 Paved Yes 18 mph (or reduce speed by 10%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Document ObjectId String Array Double Double String String String String String String String String
Data format	JSON		
Security requirements	Non-encrypted data transfer		
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests		

3.2.14.3.1 Interface specifications

Int14.1: Micro-mobility hazards mapper with speed advisory module

This component may use micro-mobility hazards mapper output (i.e. potholes and obstacles) as this data can be obtained as JSON files and saved in a local database. First, the majority of this data will be obtained to train a safe speed detection machine learning model. Then, this data can be accessed on regular basis (depending on the availability of real time data) to update the safe speed map.

Int14.2: Accident data processing and analysis module with speed advisory module

In case the micro-mobility hazards mapper data is not available, the labelled graph data for the study can be obtained and risk data related to the edges can be used. So, this data can be extracted as JSON files from the labelled graph data and saved in a local database to be used in this component.

Int14.3: External provider with speed advisory module

This component uses data obtained from external providers, such as OpenStreetMap, to enhance the micro-mobility hazards mapper data or the labelled graph data. This data includes road maximum speed, type and category and it can be extracted as JSON files for the study area and saved in a local database to be used in this component.

Int14.4: Speed advisory module with SMDS

As a result of implementing the component, the generated (or updated) safe speed map will be exported and saved in the micro-mobility data space as JSON files. This result mainly includes the location (i.e. road edge, segment or section) and maximum speed limit.

3.2.14.4 Deployment approach

A local server was selected rather than relying on cloud-based services for full control over data flow from the various data sources to the speed advisory module without external dependencies.

3.2.14.5 Testing

Table 81. Results of testing the speed advisory module

Description	Result
Sample payloads were created to test the responses from the API endpoints and websites and specifically, labelled graph RestAPI to collect edge-based risk data in Dresden and wider Saxony area.	Achieved
Unit testing was adopted to ensure the following interfaces: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ interface with OpenStreetMap – OMS to collect road data ▪ interface with the micro-mobility hazards mapper to get the road and traffic hazards data ▪ interface to the SMDS to store the output of the component. 	Ongoing

3.2.14.6 Non-functional requirements

Table 82. Non-functional requirements for the speed advisory module

Availability	The component must always be operational. Non-availability of the component may impact the speed advise provided to end-users and may impact the safety of VRUs.
Capacity	The component can provide a safe speed map / advice based on real time data collected from micro-vehicles and micro-mobility users. The component may be triggered every five minutes to update the safe speed map and store it in the database so it can be accessed by other components. Alternatively, a static safe speed map can be provided if real time data is not available.
Latency	The maximum acceptable time for generating/updating the safe speed map should not be more than 60 sec.
Monitoring	The availability of the component can be monitored by requests every five minutes. All requests and responses can be logged.
Extensibility	The component will support various data sources and types. However, additional data sources and types may be integrated in the future.
Portability	The solution can be deployed and implemented (may be with some minor amendments related to the input data) in all the LLs, if input data is available.

3.2.15 Safety-oriented proactivity and nudge engine

3.2.15.1 Component overview

The safety-oriented proactivity and nudge engine (nudge engine from here on) is a behavioural intelligence module designed to enhance road safety for VRUs by promoting proactive and context-aware decision-making. Based in behavioural science, the nudge engine delivers real-time suggestions guiding users toward safer travel behaviours without being intrusive or disruptive. These nudges are contextually selected and transmitted to users based on a set of criteria (e.g. personal, situational, environmental factors) thereby supporting users before, during, and after their trips. The nudge engine operates as a backend standalone service within the SOTERIA ecosystem and is fully integrated with the SOTERIA mobile application. It receives real-time trip data from the app and combines it with static and dynamic safety inputs such as accident hotspots, hazard maps (stemming from the SMDS) and user profile information (from the SOTERIA mobile application) to determine appropriate safety prompts. The messages are categorised into three types: pre-trip (e.g. safety reminders), on-trip (e.g. risk alerts), and post-trip (e.g. behavioural feedback, positive affirmation). By functioning as an assistive safety tool, the nudge

engine contributes directly to the project's goal of reducing accident risks for micro-mobility users and VRUs through subtle, personalised interventions.

3.2.15.2 Design

Figure 24 Nudge engine information flow

3.2.15.3 Interfaces

Table 83: Interfaces of nudge engine

Interface #	Source component	Destination component	Interface type
Int15.1	Firebase backend	Nudge engine	API calls
Int15.2	SOTERIA SMDS	Nudge engine	Direct file transfer
Int15.3	Nudge engine	Firebase backend	API calls

Table 84: Summary of Int15.1 [Firebase backend to nudge engine]

Data description	User profile information and preference settings (impairment type, preferred communication mode, frequency of nudges, travel habits)
Data model / sample	<pre>{ "userId": "123", "tripStatus": "pre-trip",</pre>

	<pre>"language": "en" "location": { "latitude": 40.712776, "longitude": -74.005974 }, "speed": 0, "userProfile": { "primaryTransportMode": "pedestrian" }, }</pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	HTTPS through Firebase native encryption (advanced security)
Invocation frequency	Pre-trip, on-trip and post-trip requests for safety nudges towards the user

Table 85: Summary of Int15.2 (SOTERIA SMDS to nudge engine)

Data description	Contextual hazard data, including known accident hotspots and geo-referenced risk indicators
Data model / sample	<pre>{ "hotspot_id": 6995411, "longitude": 12.5876423, "latitude": 51.5934464, "accident_count": 6, "risk_score": "1" }, { "hotspot_id": 9782154, "longitude": 13.0010749, "latitude": 51.5612697, "accident_count": 9, "risk_score": "5" }, { "hotspot_id": 9936869, "longitude": 12.9883011, "latitude": 51.5593212, "accident_count": 6, "risk_score": "4" }, { "hotspot_id": 10981473, "longitude": 12.9979489, "latitude": 51.5472036, "accident_count": 5, "risk_score": "1" } }</pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	Access-controlled file transfer

Invocation frequency	Yearly
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Table 86: Summary of Int15.3 (Nudge engine to Firebase backend)

Data description	Safety message sent to the user and optional metadata for post-trip feedback or logging
Data model / sample	<p>Post-trip API call</p> <pre> { "userId": 123, "tripStatus": "post-trip", "language": "en", "location": { "latitude": 40.712776, "longitude": -74.005974 }, "speed": 20, "userProfile": { "primaryTransportMode": "pedestrian" } } </pre> <p>Post-trip API response</p> <pre> { "message": "Following traffic rules makes a big difference. You're helping create safer roads for everyone." } </pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	HTTPS communication via Firebase admin Software Development Kit (SDK) with authenticated service credentials
Invocation frequency	Triggered in response to app requests (pre-, on-, post-trip) or for storage / logging of delivered nudges

3.2.15.3.1 Interface specifications

Int16.1: Firebase backend with nudge engine

The nudge engine accesses Firebase Firestore to retrieve user-specific information, including language preferences, impairment type, preferred nudge frequency, and mobility profile. This data is used to personalise the safety messages delivered to the user. API calls to Firebase are typically initiated during pre-trip, post-trip or on-trip phases to ensure that nudges align with the current user context. Data is retrieved in JSON format and parsed by the nudge engine for message filtering and prioritisation.

Int16.2: SOTERIA SMDS with nudge engine

The nudge engine fetches contextual hazard data, including known accident hotspots and geo-referenced risk indicators, from the SMDS. This interface supports on-trip nudging by enabling the system to issue timely warnings when users approach areas with a high concentration of past incidents. The data is retrieved periodically and cached within the nudge engine to allow fast, asynchronous access during real-time operations.

Int16.3: Nudge Engine with Firebase backend

Following a completed trip or when a nudge is generated, the nudge engine may interact with Firebase to store the delivered message and associated metadata for logging or analytical purposes. This allows for traceability, feedback tracking, and improved message relevance over time. These calls are also used to support post-trip feedback functionality and to align with impact assessment metrics defined under WP4 | Demonstrations of SOTERIA safe solutions.

3.2.15.4 Deployment approach

A local server was selected rather than relying on cloud-based services for full control over data flow from the various data sources to the speed advisory module without external dependencies.

3.2.15.5 Testing

Table 87. Results of testing the nudge engine

Description	Result
Sample request and response payloads were created to test the API endpoints for each nudge type (pre-trip, on-trip, post-trip).	Achieved
Unit testing was conducted on the message selection logic to verify contextual prioritisation, timing conditions, and multilingual message delivery.	Ongoing
Integration tests were performed to validate communication between the SOTERIA mobile app and the nudge engine via asynchronous API calls.	Achieved
API schema extensions were tested to support additional input variables and output structures.	Achieved
Load testing was conducted on the Dockerised backend to validate scalability and performance on the SOTERIA server.	Ongoing

3.2.15.6 Non-functional requirements

Table 88. Non-functional requirements for the nudge engine

Availability	The component must remain continuously operational during pilot phases. Temporary unavailability may lead to loss of real-time nudging and reduced safety support for users.
Capacity	The service must be capable of handling multiple simultaneous requests from different users and trip contexts, maintaining consistent response time and message delivery accuracy.
Latency	The maximum acceptable response time for generating and returning a nudge message should not exceed one second under typical operating conditions.
Monitoring	System availability and performance are monitored through internal logs and external probes. Error logs and message delivery timestamps are recorded for troubleshooting and feedback analysis.
Extensibility	The nudge engine is modular in design, allowing the inclusion of new message types, risk sources, or user preference variables without architectural overhaul.
Protection	All user data is handled in compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) principles. Data is anonymised when not essential to message logic, and all communication is encrypted via HTTPS. User consent mechanisms are enforced at app level.
Other notes	Nudge frequency settings were added to address concerns around over-alerting. The system remains operational even when external inputs are unavailable by using cached hotspot data and contextual defaults.

3.2.16 User information services

3.2.16.1 Component overview

SOTERIA mobile application acts as the primary user interface for accessing SOTERIA’s safety services. Core features of the latest version include a secure authentication and authorisation via custom credentials or OAuth (via Google email), profiling and settings management, route visualisation and navigation through focused safety measures.

3.2.16.2 Design

Figure 25: SOTERIA mobile application description diagram

3.2.16.3 Interfaces

Table 89: Interfaces of user information services component

Interface #	Source component	Destination component	Interface type
Int16.1	SOTERIA mobile application	Firebase backend	Firebase native API calls
Int16.2	SOTERIA mobile application	Google API geolocation services	API calls
Int16.3	Firebase backend	Journey planner	API calls
Int16.4	Firebase backend	Nudge engine	API calls

Table 90: Summary of Int16.1 (SOTERIA mobile application to Firebase backend)

Data description	Authorisation, profiling, settings of application
Data model / sample	<pre>{ "communication_mode_with_user": "text", "created_at": "June 26, 2025 at 11:47:27 AM UTC+3", "email": "testuser@test.com", "email_verified": false, "environmental_concerns": "all", "frequency_of_travel": "daily", "google_verified": true, "home_address": "Albertstraße 3, Dresden, Dresden-Neustadt, Germany", "impairment": "no_impairment", "primary_mode_of_transport": "bike", "profile_complete": true, "residential_area_type": "suburban", "safety_slider": 80, "safety_tips_frequency": "frequently", "terms_accepted": true, }</pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	Firestore native encryption (advanced security)
Invocation frequency	Ad-hoc requests on interactions of user with the application.

Table 91: Summary of Int16.2 (SOTERIA mobile application to Google API geolocation services)

Data description	Geolocation services, maps information
Data model / sample	<pre>{ "location": { "lat": 37.4219983, "lng": -122.084 }, "accuracy": 1200.4 }</pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	Google native encryption (advanced security)
Invocation frequency	Requests regarding location and mobility data during navigation.

Table 92. Summary of Int16.3 (Firebase backend to journey planner)

Data description	Route investigation from point A to point B
Data model / sample	<pre> { "modes": ["walking",], "travelTime": 1260, "distance": 4290, "api": "Here", "localStartTime": "2025-07-23T13:13:27+0200", "startTime": 1728472620, "legs": [{ "isPT": false, "id": "v5a4m53r01p001c7jw1guqem", "distance": 450, "travelTime": 480, "mode": "walking", "startTime": 1728472620, "waitingTime": 0, "steps": [{ "distance": 408, "travelTime": 420, "points": [[-3.705483, 40.413757], [-3.705451, 40.413979]] } ] }] } </pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	HTTPS through Firebase native encryption (advanced security)
Invocation frequency	Route options request from point A to point B.

Table 93. Summary of Int16.4 (Firebase backend to nudge engine)

Data description	Automatic request during route navigation
Data model / sample	<pre> { "userId": "123", "tripStatus": "on-trip", "language": "en", "location": { "latitude": 40.712776, "longitude": -74.005974 }, "speed": 5, "userProfile": { "primaryTransportMode": "pedestrian" }, "hotspotMessage": true, } </pre>
Data format	JSON
Security requirements	HTTPS through Firebase native encryption (advanced security)
Invocation frequency	Pre-trip, on-trip and post-trip requests for safety nudges towards the user.

3.2.16.3.1 Interface specifications

Int17.1: SOTERIA mobile application with Firebase backend

The mobile application uses Firebase to handle core user-related functionalities such as authentication, profile creation, and settings storage. Firebase also supports authorisation workflows via OAuth (e.g. Google login), enabling secure access management. These operations are handled through Firebase native APIs and are triggered based on user interaction.

Int17.2: SOTERIA Mobile Application with Google API geolocation services

During navigation or location-based interactions, the mobile app communicates with Google geolocation APIs to retrieve real-time positioning and map-related data. These services support route visualisation, map rendering, and contextual awareness for safety functions such as hotspot alerts and hazard proximity notifications.

Int17.3: Firebase Bbackend with journey planner

When the user requests a new route, the Firebase backend relays the request to the journey planner module. This communication supports the retrieval of optimal, safe routes from point A to point B, including multimodal options. The planner returns route options enriched with SOTERIA-specific safety attributes.

Int17.4: Firebase backend with nudge engine

Throughout the user journey, the backend interacts with the nudge engine to retrieve relevant safety messages. This interaction occurs in pre-trip, on-trip, and post-trip phases, depending on user actions and contextual triggers. The messages returned are tailored to the user’s profile, location, and real-time status.

3.2.16.4 Deployment approach

SOTERIA mobile application will be available for downloading and installation in an Android device, through Google Play Store with access provided only by invitation.

3.2.16.5 Testing

Table 94. Results of testing the user information services

Description	Result
Unit testing was adopted to ensure UI consistency across different devices.	Achieved
Finalised payloads were created to interact with Backend APIs, internal, and external services.	Achieved

3.2.16.6 Non-functional requirements

Table 95. Non-functional requirements for the user information services

Availability	The component must always remain operational when the device has online access.
Capacity	Application is designed to operate with about 1000 users per hour.
Latency	The maximum acceptable time for visualizing the route options must not exceed more that 15 seconds.
Monitoring	Users’ interactions with the mobile application such us route requests, completed trips or profile changes are logged and can be monitored through SOTERIA Backend.
Extensibility	The component is developed with clear architecture and has the ability to be rapidly extended by more than one person.
Protection	Encryption is applied to all stored data and communications between internal and external services.
Other notes	-

4 Conclusions

Deliverable D1.4 presents a comprehensive framework that supports the deployment of advanced safety solutions for VRUs and micro-mobility services in urban environments. The main achievement of this deliverable is the development of a modular and interoperable system architecture comprising 16 components. These components collectively enable real-time data acquisition, accident prediction, behavioural analysis, safety advisory mechanisms, and user-centred information services. The integration of AI, Deep Learning, and XAI models ensures transparency and accountability in the system’s decision-making processes, while the sensor kits and routing engines promote dynamic and adaptive interventions in complex urban environments.

Another significant contribution is the introduction of the Safe City Certification framework, which assesses urban safety through a multidimensional approach that includes physical, digital, social, and systemic factors. This methodology enhances the field by integrating objective data with subjective perceptions to evaluate safety performance and enable transparent comparisons between urban districts. Its flexibility allows for integration into municipal dashboards and urban planning processes, facilitating long-term sustainability and scalability.

The technological developments of SOTERIA, outlined in this deliverable, will be demonstrated at the LLS to assess their effectiveness in enhancing urban safety. The findings from this evaluation will be presented in deliverable D4.3 | Solutions impact assessment resulting from the activities of WP4 | Demonstration of SOTERIA safe solutions.

References

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